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**INNOVATIVE PRACTICES
IN BANKING, IT,
EDUCATION AND SOCIAL
SCIENCE**

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Paper 1

MANAGEMENT OF UNIVERSAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR REDEFINING INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTIVITY AND PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

It is observed that certain technologies have grown and expanded their branches to many areas and sectors of practice in such a way that they have been designated as General-Purpose Technologies. Such general-purpose technologies are identified and used in many industries to do business and to solve or simplify the problems of industries. During the last few years, it is observed that out of many general-purpose technologies, two technologies have shown accelerated growth and gave birth to many underlying sub-technologies: (1) Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT), and (2) Nanotechnology (NT). These two technologies are further identified as “Universal Technologies” due to their potential capability of solving problems related to basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human beings in society. ICCT and Nanotechnology have opened up the possibility of ubiquitous solutions to many problems related to production and service industries by offering automated mobility, stability, and sustainability. In this paper, we have identified various strategies for effective management of ICCT & NT underlying technologies in solving issues pertaining to basic needs, advanced wants, and dreamy desires of human beings in society. The paper also discusses how these universal technologies can be unified to further strengthen their abilities in redefining the productivity in production-related industries and performance in service-related industries with the objective of moving towards technological singularity by building super-intelligent self-replicating machines.

Keywords : Universal technologies, Technology management, Strategic management of technologies, ICCT, Nanotechnology, Technological singularity, Technological unification, Redefining productivity & performance.

1. INTRODUCTION :

Technology management is an area of Management Science where business organizations plan and implement their technology development and adoption strategy by means of predicting and foreseeing the future changes so that to create a technology roadmap for competition, sustainability, and growth & prosper. Technology management is a part of corporate strategic management and organizations should identify a suitable strategy to compete in its industry by adopting a suitable strategy. Strategic management is a branch of management which consists of various well-structured and implementable ideas to ensure success in any decision-making process of that management level. Strategic management usually consists of some short cut methods in the decision-making process of a manager to ensure winning. Strategic management principles can be applied at operations level, business level, corporate or industry levels. The strategies followed at the operational level of an organization to improve productivity or efficiency in production organization or service organizations respectively are called operational strategy. Operational level strategies are also

called functional strategies due to the reason that they are used in functional areas of the organizations. The various operational strategies include Design of Goods and Services, Quality Management, Process and Capacity Design, Location Strategy, Layout Design and Strategy, Human Resources and Job Design, Supply Chain Management, Inventory Management, etc. The strategies followed at the business level for new product or service innovations in production organization or service organization respectively is called business strategy. The various business strategies include Cost leadership, Aggressive marketing for enhancing sales, Product/service differentiation, Pricing strategy, and gaining technological advantages using emerging suitable technology. The strategies followed by an organization at corporate or industry level are called corporate strategy. These include growth strategy, expansion & diversification strategies, partnership strategies, Business stabilization strategies, Technology adoption strategies, Online business strategies, etc.

As well known in business management, management decision making is nothing but (1) identifying a issue as per the objective of the organization, (2) analysing the issue to discover the problems, (3) Synthesize the possible solutions or ideas for the problems, (4) Choose an optimum solutions using Quantitative analysis/operations research, (5) Implementing the optimum solution to get expected results as benefits. In this paper, the process of identification of emerging technologies based on analysing technologies using universal technology concept and the steps in adopting such technologies for realizing the organizational objectives of increasing productivity and/or enhancing performance.

2. RELATED WORK :

Many scholarly published research works is reported in the areas like technology management, strategies to manage technology, universal technologies, redefining productivity & performance, and strategic management of technologies. The review of related publications obtained from google scholar search is listed in table 1.

Table 1 : Review of related work

S.No.	Area of Work	Focus	Reference
1	Technology management	Art of high-technology management	Maidique, M. A. et al. (1984). [1]
2	Technology management	Based on process thinking	Gregory, M. J. (1995). [2]
3	Technology management	Information technology management through knowledge transfer approach.	Bolisani, E. et al. (1999). [3]
4	Technology management	Understanding technology management as a dynamic capability through the lens of dynamic capabilities theory	Cetindamar, D., et al. (2009). [4]
5	Technology management	Strategic management of technology	Harris, J. M., et al. (1983). [5]
6	Technology management	Developing strategy for product innovation	Cooper, R. G. (2000). [6]
7	Technology management	Design of products as per customer needs	Igor Ansoff, H. (1987). [7]
8	Technology management	Strategy for technology transfer	Bone, S., et al. (2,000). [8]
9	Technology management	Innovative classification of methods of the Future-oriented Technology Analysis	Halicka, K. (2016). [9]
10	Technology	Integrating digital technologies to drive	Kane, G. C. (2015).

	management	the business	[10]
11	Strategies to manage technology	A framework to manage the innovation strategies of new technology based firms	Davey, S. M. et al. (2011). [11]
12	Strategies to manage technology	The lessons of failure: learning to manage new manufacturing technology & capabilities needed to acquire technologies by firms	Bessant, J. (1993). [12]
13	Strategies to manage technology	Managing operations and information technology	Hayes, R. (2006). [13]
14	Strategies to manage technology	Alternative conceptual lenses and be prepared to continuously make adaptations	Henderson, J. C. et al (1999). [14]
15	Strategies to manage technology	Alignment between IT strategies and the openness of open innovation strategies	Cui, T. et al. (2015). [15]
16	Universal technologies	When technologies converge and regulatory models diverge	Frieden, R. M. (1999). [16]
17	Universal technologies	ICCT and Nanotechnologies as universal technologies	Aithal P. S. et al. (2019) [17]
18	Redefining productivity & performance	Redefining productivity through inter-firm operations and supply chains	Scerri, M., et al (2011). [18]
19	Redefining productivity & performance	Redefining hospital performance	Dailey, R. C. (1988). [19]
20	Redefining productivity & performance	Rethinking and redefining the determinants of corporate profitability	Batra, R. et al. (2016). [20]
21	Strategic management of technologies	External resource leverage are the keys to effective technology	Roberts, E. B. (2001). [21]
22	Strategic management of technologies	Deals with the rise and character of modern technology strategy	Friar, J. et al. (1985). [22]
23	Strategic management of technologies	Strategies to effective management of technology	Antoniou, P. H. (2004). [23]
24	Strategic management of technologies	New approaches	Mitchell, G. R. (1985). [24]

25	Strategic management of technologies	Strategic perspectives of corporate sustainability management to develop a sustainable organization	Baumgartner, R. J. et al. (2017). [25]
26	Strategic management of technologies	Reinventing innovation management research in a digital world	Nambisan, S. et al. (2017). [26]
27	Strategic management of technologies	A framework for diagnosing and improving digital product and service innovation	Nylén, D. et al. (2017). [27]
28	Strategic management of technologies	Strategic Management Models & Indian Epics	Aithal, P. S. (2016). [28]

3. OBJECTIVES & METHODOLOGY :

The objective of this paper is to analyse and synthesize various strategies required to identify and monitor, adapt, and manage emerging technologies that can redefine the business processes for an organization. Following are the specific objectives identified and addressed :

- (1) To know various strategies available to manage General Purpose technologies to fulfil their goal
- (2) To identify the objectives of Universal technologies emerged recently
- (3) To analyse the purview of Information Communication & Computation technology (ICCT) in solving the problems and supporting the advancement of civilization.
- (4) To analyse the purview of Nanotechnology in solving the problems and supporting the advancement of civilization.
- (5) To discuss how ICCT and Nanotechnologies work together as complementary and unified technologies.
- (6) To redefine the objectives of productivity of Manufacturing industries using unified universal technologies.
- (7) To redefine the objectives of the performance of Service industries using unified universal technologies.
- (8) To predict the technological singularity level of unified universal technologies through a technology roadmap.

The methodology adopted is a conceptual analysis by means of scanning strategic business models and emerging technologies that can re-define the business processes through their innovativeness and customer satisfying abilities. The data/information related to present strategies and emerging technologies are collected from Google scholar and other social research networks and analysed using predictive analysis methods to study the effect of emerging technologies on enhancing organizational productivity/performance in manufacturing or service organizations respectively.

4. Strategic Management Models for New General Purpose Technologies :

Technology is essential ingredient of every business organization to survive from disasters, sustain for long term in the business, differentiate themselves, convert as monopoly, and for grow and prosper. Organizations are advised to monitor emerging technologies which are affecting the organizational business in future days in an intelligent way using some

predictive models. Organization should be capable to identify suitable technology which can help to use all five kinds of strategies commonly used at business and industry levels.

Technology is an application of science and used to solve many complicated challenges in society to make human life comfortable and happy. Certain technologies have grown and expanded their branches to many areas and sectors of practice in such a way that they have been designated as General-Purpose Technologies. Such general-purpose technologies are identified and used in many industries to do business and to solve or simplify the problems of industries.

GPT's are characterized by (1) Pervasiveness – The GPT should spread to most sectors. (2) Improvement – The GPT should get better over time and, hence, should keep lowering the costs of its users. (3) Innovation Opportunity – The GPT should support to invent and produce new products or processes. Whole eras of technical progress and growth appear to be driven by a few 'General Purpose Technologies' (GPT's), such as the Steam engine, Electric motor, Semiconductors based devices, etc [29].

In all the three organizational levels, technology management is an essential strategy for survival, sustainability, differentiation, monopoly, and growth & expansion. The adoption and management of technology is crucial to every organization and is the lifeblood of the organization to keep it sustainable. The technology management includes identifying and implementing the technology which can support the organization for enhancing its productivity and performance in the local and global business environment.

5. Universal Technologies :

It is observed that some of the general purpose technologies are grown as umbrella technologies and gave birth to many sub technologies under them as underlying technologies to solve basic and advanced problems of the society to make the life of human being comfortable. These underlying technologies are growing both horizontally and vertically to solve (1) basic problems like nutritious food, clean water for drinking and irrigation, low cost durable shelters, low cost, reliable and renewable energy for individuals, homes, transports, and industries, quality basic education for everybody, affordable health services; (2) advanced problems like easy & affordable access to products and services related to everyone's daily needs for easy & comfortable life with happiness; (3) dreamy desires related problems like flying, space travel, virtual reality, life span expansion, and much more fantasy including antiaging and achieving immortality. The technology which supports to solve the problems related to the above three areas are called universal technology. Thus, universal technologies either alone or with other general purpose technologies are capable of solving all kinds of problems in the society. Based on scanning the technologies of the 21st century, it is identified that two general purpose technologies have grown to support many underlying technologies and shown their capabilities to solve almost any problems in society at all the three levels. These two technologies identified as universal technologies are Information Communication and Computation Technology (ICCT) [30-31] and Nanotechnology (NT) [32-34]. Both these universal technologies have many underlying technologies and these underlying technologies are also capable to grow as killer technology in their application areas.

5.1 ICCT Underlying Technologies :

Information Communication & Computation Technology (ICCT) is a Technology to generate, transmit, process, store, and deliver information in the electronic or optical signal format. Mainly of these are used for intangible applications in various industry sectors both for managing and controlling various processes.

(1) Artificial Intelligence & Robotics

- (2) Big Data & Intelligence Technology
- (3) Blockchain Technology
- (4) Cloud Computing Technology
- (5) Cyber Security Technology
- (6) 3D Printing Technology
- (7) Digital Marketing Technology
- (8) Internet & Internet of Things (IOT)
- (9) Information Storage Technology
- (10) Optical Computing Technology
- (11) Online Education Technology
- (12) Virtual and Augmented Reality

Fig. 1 : Block diagram representing various underlying technologies of ICCT [30]

Applications of ICCT underlying Technologies :

ICCT underlying technologies are used for developing machines which can understand, plan, think, compare, and decide like human beings using artificial intelligence technology (AIT). They can also communicate, monitor, and control the devices interconnected using the internet of things technology (IoT). They can analyse and compare, and identify the intelligence for business using Big data & Intelligence technology. The machines can keep track of information or financial transactions which can completely eliminate fraud and corruption in the society using Blockchain technology. Human beings and machines can make use of distant hardware devices, software, and other applications without owning them and as rental facilities using cloud computing technology. The secrecy & security of the information stored, transmitted, and processed can be maintained using cyber security technology. As technology progress and aspirations of people enhance, more and more data and information storage facilities are required and can be realized using information storage technology. Development of high speed computers are continuously in demand for integrating computational processes support the entire world using optical computers and cloud computing technologies so that few computers are enough to maintain world information

processing requirement. Any device or structure made of any material or mix of materials in any size can be produced by three-dimensional printing layer by layer to produce real devices and systems using 3D Printing technology. The companies in any industry and individuals can sell their products and services to entire globe by means low cost, affordable marketing using the internet called digital marketing technology. ICCT also allows ubiquitous education & training systematically using online education technologies and models so that off-campus education in any area and at any level are possible. Virtual reality technology allows to create an artificial environment to mimic the real situations with the help of a computer machine and presented to a user in such a way that the user suspends the belief and accepts it as a real environment. Table 2 lists some of the prominent applications of ICCT underlying technologies in industries and for individuals in society.

Table 2 : Prominent applications of ICCT underlying technologies

S. No.	ICCT Underlying Technologies	Prominent Applications
1	Artificial Intelligence & Robotics	Creating intelligent machines which can understand, plan, think, compare, and decide like human beings. The objective is to create super intelligent machines which can mimic the actions of human brain and overtake human intelligence.
2	Big Data & Intelligence Technology	Continuous data generated at high speed from CCD's and business processes are analysed by means of descriptive analytics, predictive analytics, and prescriptive analytics to find intelligence and relationship associated with them for futuristic decisions.
3	Blockchain Technology	Protects the information or documents related to a chain of transactions so that all and every previous transaction related to a digital document or digital currency so that any kind of fraud or corruption can be totally eliminated.
4	Cloud Computing Technology	Use of external hardware, software, or software applications ubiquitously by a company or individuals as rented or free facility for used time so that physical owning of such facilities can be eliminated. This will optimize the utilization of any digital storage and processing device by sharing with other users globally for rent.
5	Cyber Security Technology	Used for providing the security and secrecy of data, information in digital devices during processing, storing, and transmission stages as well for identifying the actual user of a system. Cyber security technology has responsibility to protect computers, networks, programs, and data for any kind of exploitation from unauthorized access or attacks.
6	3D Printing Technology	Using 3D Printing technology, any device or structure made of any material including, plastic, rubber, metals, mud, cement, or their mixtures in any proportion and in any size can be fabricated layer by layer into a three

		dimensional structure to produce real devices and systems.
7	Digital Marketing Technology	Digital marketing technology allows the companies and individuals to sell their products and services to entire world by means low cost, affordable ubiquitous marketing techniques using internet.
8	Internet & Internet of Things (IOT)	Internet of things technology (IoT) is used to communicate, control, and monitor various digital devices used in home, office, and company environment interconnected using internet. IOT has major application in interconnecting various cyber-physical systems in industry 4.0.
9	Information Storage Technology	This technology supports the development of high density digital and optical storage devices of capability Terabytes, Petabytes, Exabytes, Zettabytes, and Yottabytes.
10	Optical Computing Technology	Fabrication of high speed optical computers based on optical signal switching and optical signal processing using optical logic gates and flip-flops by means suitable materials/devices.
11	Online Education Technology	Allows to transform traditional campus based education into Massive Online Open Courses (MOOC) based education. Ex : EDX, COUSERA, NPTEL, SWAYAM, etc.
12	Virtual and Augmented Reality	Create an artificial environment to mimic the real situations with the help of a computer machine and presented to a user in such a way that the user suspends the belief and accepts it as a real environment. It has applications in entertainment and education. Augmented reality is a pseudo or mixed reality of real and virtual worlds by the assistance of a computer-generated perceptual information and used to enhance customer experience in business services.

The above ICCT underlying technologies are capable to solve many problems related to human comfortability and dreamy desires. These underlying technologies along with a suitable manufacturing technology can do marvel to solving many problems of the individuals of society. ICCT at its nascent stage, is expected to support the production of super intelligent machines which can replace human employees by robots in many industries.

5.2 Nanotechnology Underlying Technologies :

Nanotechnology is another general purpose technology supports manufacturing of various products using special properties of Nanoparticles (10^{-9} m). It is a manufacturing technology with potential ability to improve the features of existing products and to produce new products in various fields. Nanotechnology has many subfields called nanotechnology underlying technologies. Nanotechnology is a boon to the mankind if handled carefully. Nanotechnology is capable to solve problems of basic types, advanced problems related to human comfortability, and even problems related to dreamy desires if used with other application type technologies like ICCT. Nanotechnology can solve problems related to

providing nutritious food by producing artificial food, converting environmental water and sea water into drinking water in large scale using renewable energy, providing low cost and strong shelters at low cost, low cost renewable energy to required amount, solutions to low cost and durable transportation facility, durable consumer products and textiles, easy health and medical solutions. Nanotechnology at its nascent stage, is expected to support for the production of self-replicating nanomachines which can further build any structure as per the requirement. The important underlying technologies of nanotechnology are listed below :

- (1) Nanomaterials development Technology
- (2) Nanomechanics Technology
- (3) Nanoelectronics Technology
- (4) Nanophotonics Technology
- (5) Nanobiotechnology
- (6) Nanomedicine

Applications of Nanotechnology underlying Technologies :

Nanomaterials of suitable type and properties are used in Nanotechnology treated Seeds in Agriculture, in food packets, production of artificial food, Customized location focused rain and large scale production of drinking water from sea & environment, nanomaterial fabricated textiles with many special properties, nanomaterial based cosmetics, paints, consumer durables, building materials, improving products quality, durability in many industries, etc. Nanomechanics Technology is used in manufacturing equipment, nanoelectromechanical systems (NEMS) etc. Nanoelectronics Technology is used in production and use of nanodiodes, nanotransistors, Nano integrated circuits, and nanostructure based electronic memories. Nanophotonics Technology deals with nanomaterial based solar cells, optical memories, optical computers, etc. Nanobiotechnology deals with bio-medical applications of nanomaterials including drug delivery, targeted therapy, Gene delivery, Molecular imaging, Bio-marker mapping, detection & diagnosis of diseases etc. Nanomedicine has subareas like biological imaging for diagnostics, Biosensors for toxin detection, Regenerative medicine, Medical robotics, nanobots, Tissue engineering, Drug delivery, cancer therapy, surgery, etc. Apart from above, nanotechnology has its roots in many different areas to solve basic problems, advanced requirements, and dreamy desires along with other technologies including ICT. Such breakthrough technologies of the 21st century include :

- (i) Nanotechnology treated Seeds for Innovations in Agriculture
- (ii) Universal drinking water system
- (iii) Automobiles
- (iv) Renewable energy system
- (v) Optical computation
- (vi) Embedded intelligence
- (vii) Chameleon chips
- (viii) Space Travel
- (ix) Anticipated Immortality

Table 3 : Prominent applications of NT underlying technologies

S. No.	Underlying Technologies	Prominent Applications
1	Nanomaterials development Technology	Applications related to Nanometal chemistry, Nanostructured polymers, Nanocomposites, etc for cosmetics, textiles, consumer products, agriculture,

		food processing and packaging, water filters, etc.
2	Nanomechanics Technology	Deals with mechanical properties (kinetic, thermal, and elastic) of physical systems having nanometer material involved in them. Used in nanotriology for friction, wears and contact mechanics at nano scale electromagnetic systems, and nanofluidics. Many kinds of chemical compounds, advanced mechanical motors, UPS and high-power batteries, horsepower, acidic fuels, rust disinfectants, Nanotubes and Carbon Nanowires, Nanolithography, Nanomanufacturing, Nanolithography, and other areas of manufacturing.
3	Nanoelectronics Technology	Nanofabrication, Nanoprocessors, nanotransistors, Nanoelectronic components for high temperature, ultra - low power, biologically friendly packaging, Nanoelectronic memories, etc.
4	Nanophotonics Technology	Nanocomputers, Nanosensors, Nanoprobes, fluorescent imaging, sensitization, nanolithography. All optical processors, Bio-imaging, Energy conversion, Molecular manipulation, Data storage, Display devices, etc.
5	Nanobiotechnology	Pre-clinical Testing of Novel Nano Medical tools, Diagnostic Tools and Applications, Tissue, Cell and Genetic Engineering involving Nano Medical Tools, Protein detection, genome sequencing, proteomics, imaging, nanobots, and self-replicating; pesticide delivery systems through bioactive nanoencapsulation; biosensors to detect and quantify pathogens; organic compounds, etc.
6	Nanomedicine	Therapeutic advancements using Nano-medicine and Research Techniques, Development of Nano Drug Delivery Systems, Cancer treatment, Gene therapy, treatment of neurodegenerative disorders, operative dentistry, Antibacterial treatment, Ophthalmology, Surgery, Tissue engineering, Regenerative medicine, Cell repair, Medicated textiles, etc.

6. Unification of ICCT & Nanotechnologies :

It can be argued that the nanotechnology underlying technologies and ICCT underlying technologies are related and depending on each other. Nanotechnology is manufacturing technology and ICCT is an application technology. The innovations in nanotechnology support innovations in ICCT and Opportunities in ICCT stimulates innovations in Nanotechnology. Thus, nanotechnology and ICCT are complementary and interdependent technologies. When these two technologies are studied together, the researchers will get a better idea to innovate in their thinking to solve many kinds of problems in society. The term unification is used to combine two or more things which can be used together to solve a problem. Unification of two technologies means these two technologies can be used together to get a complete solution to a real-world problem. Unification of ICCT and Nanotechnologies leads to an accelerated growth of these technologies and innovations in

nanotechnology support further innovations in ICCT or vice versa. Such unified technology also allows them to solve basic problems, advanced problems and dreamy desires of the peoples of society. Such unification leads to universal technology as discussed in section 5.

Table 4 : ICCT and NT underlying technologies which show complementary properties for unification

S. No.	NT Underlying Technologies	ICCT Underlying Technologies
1	Nanomaterials development Technology	Artificial Intelligence, 3D Printing, Blockchain,
2	Nanomechanics Technology	Internet of Things, Artificial Intelligence
3	Nanoelectronics Technology	Artificial Intelligence Data & Business Analytics, Internet of Things, Blockchain,
4	Nanophotonics Technology	Optical Computing, Blockchain,
5	Nanobiotechnology	Artificial Intelligence, 3D Printing,
6	Nanomedicine	Artificial Intelligence, Virtual Reality

7. Redefining the Manufacturing Industry based on Unified Universal Technology :

Manufacturing industry converts raw materials into finished products for basic needs, comfortable wants, and even for dreamy desires of human beings. The usage of special raw materials with ideal characteristics or improved characteristics may lead to ideal or improved products having improved properties. Similarly automating manufacturing processes with high precision and for negligible maintenance cost. Further, the final product manufactured should be an innovative product and have multi features compared to similar products available in the market. Using nanomaterials and devices as raw materials, ICCT underlying technologies like Artificial intelligence, IOT, 3D printing, etc. in the manufacturing industry sector can fulfil these possibilities. It is argued that most of the future products produced in the manufacturing industry will use nanotechnology and ICCT underlying technologies as universal technology to redefine the manufacturing industry (figure 2).

Universal Technology

8. Redefining the Service Industry based on Unified Universal Technology :

Service sector is another important sector in business management and is mainly dependent on technology. Both nanotechnology and ICCT are expected to impact heavily and creates many breakthroughs in service sectors. The nanotechnology underlying technologies like nanomedicine, nanobiotechnology, nanodevices of nanomechanics, nanoelectronics, and nanophotonics are expected to support service industry along with their complementary ICCT

underlying technologies like artificial intelligence, IOT, cloud computing, optical computers, virtual realities etc. It is strongly believed that both nanotechnology and ICCT together as universal technology will redefine the service sector present models and contribute heavily on solving problems related to the basic needs, comfortable wants, and even for dreamy desires of human beings. Thus, service industry has opportunity to adopt NT and ICCT components to improve the service quality and service features (figure 3).

Fig. 3 : Schematic representation of redefining the Service Industry based on Universal Technology

9. MANAGEMENT OF UNIVERSAL TECHNOLOGY :

The identification and implementation of suitable technologies in various business processes for a given organization is possible by means of (1) predicting future technologies, (2) anticipating the breakthrough technologies, (3) Choosing a suitable emerging technology, (4) Analysing for organizational business & corporate innovation, (5) Planning for adoption of emerging technology, (6) Analysing the cost-benefit of new technology, (7) Technology adoption, (8) Technology customization, (9) Technology monitoring & control, (10) Verifying productivity or performance, and (11) Scanning the environment for further technology breakthroughs. The systematic study of using these steps for the strategic management of technology for enhancing and controlling the productivity and performance of a given organization.

(1) Predicting future technologies :

The managers at the executive level have the responsibility of setting the future plans called the strategic plans of the organization. They should continuously monitor the changes in technology, changes in business models, and changes in customers perception with time. Predicting future technologies is a very important requirement of managing the business for sustainability.

(2) Anticipating the breakthrough technologies :

Managers while predicting future technologies need to anticipate the major breakthroughs in technology in a given time frame and plan their business investments and expansion accordingly. Breakthrough technologies may convert into killer technologies and may make the present business model or products or services obsolete.

(3) Choosing a suitable emerging technology :

Managers as decision makers to lead the organization or departments take responsibility of monitoring the external environment for possible changes in the business environment and adopt changes accordingly. When they realize the advents of technologies are going to affect the organizational performance, they should adopt such changes and if the changes are technology driven, they have a responsibility to identify an alternative which is optimum for

their organizations within their constraints by choosing a suitable emerging technology as strategic alternative.

(4) *Analysing for organizational business & corporate innovation :*

While choosing an emerging technology as a strategic alternative, managers have to analyse their present business, historical changes in their business model and its effect on their organizational performance, using various internal analysis and external analysis techniques [29]. This analysis should also involve the various innovations implemented and expected in the same industrial sector.

(5) *Planning for adoption of emerging technology :*

Based on the analysis of various alternative technologies and choosing one optimum technology, the manager should plan for adopting the new technology in organizational processes. This include short term plan and long term plan and the systematic procedure of adoption to various sections, branches, and subsidiaries.

(6) *Analysing the cost-benefit of new technology :*

The managers have responsibility on analysing the cost of such new technology based investment. In order to make use of emerging new technologies for organizational benefits, one of the techniques is to analyse the cost of adopting and implementation and its future benefits for the organization for a fixed period of time. Strategical analysis of cost-benefit will allow managers to make a decision related to the investment in new emerging technology and the speed of adoption in the organization.

(7) *Technology adoption,*

One, the organization decides to adopt a particular technology based on cost-benefit analysis, it has to identify suitable vendors to supply or to develop such technological applications.

(8) *Technology customization :*

The organization should effectively utilize the newly adopted technology as per their requirement by customizing them to be suitable for organizational use.

(9) *Technology monitoring & control :*

The purpose of technology monitoring and control is to gather information about the operational status and the capability of new technology adopted to improve the quality and efficiency of various processes and the product or service developed. A proper feedback mechanism and control based on feedback on effect of new technology should be in place to monitor organizational performance.

(10) *Verifying productivity or performance :*

This step includes the study of the effect of newly adopted technology on the efficiency and effectiveness of various organizational processes or new processes developed. The organization should develop a suitable mechanism to determine and compare the efficiency and effectiveness after the adoption of new technology with previous technology. In this process, the organization should try to measure the improvement in productivity and performance as well as the implication of such innovation on the organizational value chain as well as the brand for future growth and prosperity.

(11) *Scanning the environment for further technology breakthroughs :*

The strategic management of the universal technology model involves continuous monitoring the emerging technologies and possible technology breakthroughs in society. A strategic organization involves itself or through collaboration, involves in development of new technology which is relevant to its business area. Scanning the environment to watch the progress and foresee the changes is a continuous process for every organization competing in the global business environment.

The above eleven steps are essential as “Lifecycle stages of the model on strategic management of technology” in any organization for enhancing and controlling the productivity and performance. These lifecycle stages are essential in strategic management of technology in any organization for growth and prosperity.

10. REACHING TECHNOLOGICAL SINGULARITY :

Super intelligent machines are expected to be developed using ICCT underlying technologies and nanotechnology [35]. Similarly, nanotechnology along with ICCT underlying technologies are expected to create super human beings by modifying gene and body cells which may give rise to human immortality [36]. It is also predicted that the super intelligent machines are capable to replicate in any level of accelerated pace using a process called self-replication. The ability of self-replication of nanomachines and their super human intelligence leads to a stage so called technological singularity. It is defined as a hypothetical event in which artificial intelligence technology would be capable to build intelligent machines in the process of an intelligence explosion, that yields a super-intelligent machine which surpasses all current human control or understanding [37], [38], [39].

Thus, technological singularity is a point in the future time scale where (1) machines can think, work, and decide faster than human beings, (2) Some human beings converts themselves as super human beings using technology and achieve immortality, and (3) Direct interactions between computers and human brains leads to human- machine ubiquitous interaction. It is predicted that by the year 2050, scientists will achieve technological singularity and its consequences both positive and negative. The strategic management of technological singularity which is the consequences of Nanotechnology underlying technologies and ICCT underlying technologies is expected to play a major role in managing disasters and offering advantages related to the growth and prospers to the society.

11. CONCLUSION :

Managing technology is an important area of business management. Managing business in different industrial sectors needs the knowledge of technologies and knowledge of changes in technologies. Many general purpose technologies developed during the last few decades and supported to various industrial sectors for fast contribution to the civilized society. Technology which is an application of science to solve different problems in society is expected to reach its highest expected stage in the 21st century and gave rise to two general purpose technologies called ICCT and Nanotechnology. These two technologies are capable to solve many problems leading to optimized solutions at basic, advanced, and desired level of the society. This paper made an elaborative analysis on how the emerging general purpose technologies can grow and integrate themselves into universal technology to solve many problems in society to give a comfortable life to everyone in society. Adding further, it is essential to plan and manage these technologies in organizations systematically using our lifecycle model of technology implementation and management due to the fact that these integrated universal technologies have both positive and negative effects while using in different industries due to their anticipated capability of elevating to the technological singularity.

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Paper 2

E-BANKING SERVICES: A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO KARNATAKA BANK, MANGALURU

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Abstract:

The Indian Banking system, with one of the largest banking networks in the world, has witnessed a series of reforms over the past five years like use of E- Banking and increased participation of private sector bank. Banking today is a flourishing industry, focused on technological innovation. Banks play an important and active role in the economic development of a country. Technology is revolutionizing all areas of human endeavor and activity. It has now brought in E-banking, which is gradually replacing the traditional branch banking. Internet banking and Mobile Banking have emerged as the biggest focus and targetable areas. The customers are able to choose their banker from a number of banks offering wide range of services and delivering quality service. Internet banking and Mobile Banking are changing the banking industry and is having a significant impact on the banking relationship. Banking industry is fast growing with use of technology in the form of ATMs, online banking, telephone banking, mobile banking etc. This growth has been strongly supported by the development in the field of technology, without which this could not have been possible. Besides it will change our lifestyle in coming years. The range of services offered differs from bank to bank depending mainly on the type and size of bank. This study is conducted to know the awareness and the use of E- Banking services among Karnataka bank customers.

Keywords: Technological Innovation, E- Banking

1. INTRODUCTION:

The word bank comes from an Italian word 'banco', meaning a bench. Without a sound and effective banking system in India, it cannot have healthy economy. The banking system of India should not only be hassle free but it should be able to meet new challenges posed by the technology and any other external and internal factors. Banking system of a nation is the shadow of nation's economy. It is one of the important financial sector, which plays a vital role in the functioning of an economy. The Indian Banking system, with one of the largest banking networks in the world, has witnessed a series of reforms over the past five years like use of E- Banking and increased participation of private sector bank. Banking today is a flourishing industry, focused on technological innovation. Technology is revolutionizing all areas of human endeavor and activity. It has now brought in E-banking, which is gradually replacing the traditional branch banking. Internet banking and Mobile Banking have emerged as the biggest focus and targetable areas. Banking industry is fast growing with use of technology in the form of ATMs, online banking, telephone banking,

mobile banking etc. This growth has been strongly supported by the development in the field of technology.

Evolution of E- Banking

There have been significant developments in the e-financial services sector in the past 30 years. Until the early 1970s functional demarcation was predominant with many regulatory restrictions imposed. One main consequence of this was limited competition both domestically and internationally. As a result there was heavy reliance on traditional branch based delivery of financial services and little pressure for change. The Internet is a relatively new channel for delivering banking services. Its early form 'online banking services', requiring a PC, modem and software provided by the financial services vendors, were first introduced in the early 1980s. However, it failed to get widespread acceptance and most initiatives of this kind were discontinued. With the rapid growth of other types of electronic services since mid 1990s, banks renewed their interest in electronic modes of delivery using the Internet. The spread of online banking has coincided with the spread of high-speed broadband connections and the increasing maturation of the Internet user population.

Meaning of E-Banking:

E-banking or electronic banking refers to conducting banking activities with the help of information technology and computers. E-banking is a mix of services which include Internet banking, Mobile banking, ATM kiosks, Fund Transfer System, Real Time Gross Settlement (payment & settlement system), Credit/Debit/Smart/ Cards, Cash management services, and Data warehousing, Operational data for MIS and Customer Relationship Management. Latest innovations in technology like broadband transmission, internet access via mobiles and WebTV will further provide impetus to digital revolution.

Banking and Technology:

Technology has become the engine for triggering rapid change. It is no longer considered merely for transaction processing or confined to management information systems. It implies the integration of information system with the communication technology and of innovative application to product manufacturing, design and control. The banking sector has embraced the use of technology to serve its client's faster and also to do more with less. The basic advantage of using developments in Information and Communication Technology are handling huge volume of transactions in real time, cost minimization, better customer service, possibility of innovative and new products and services, elimination of geographical distance and barriers and efficient service.

Technology innovations by Indian bank:

Innovation normally results in the creation of a product or services that is novel to an organization. Innovations can take place in the process, service or procedure. Technological innovation service area is equally important as it is in products. Some of the innovations, which the technology has brought in banking industries, are Automated Teller Machine (ATM), mobile banking, net banking, credit/debit/smart cards, tele banking, electronic money, digital payment and digital currency.

2 OBJECTIVES:

The study was undertaken with the following objectives:

- To study the effectiveness of E- Banking channels.
- To study the customer acceptance and adoptability to E- Banking channels.
- To analyze the convenience to the customers by using E- Banking / New age banking.
- To study the awareness of E- Banking services among the customers.

3 MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

Primary Data:

Primary Data are those which are collected afresh and for the first time. Data are obtained through the direct communication with the respective person and also through the questionnaire method.

Secondary Data:

Secondary Data are those which have been already collected by someone else and which have been passed through the statistical processes. In this study data has been taken from various secondary sources like internet, books, magazines, reports, publications and journals.

4. SAMPLE AND SAMPLE SIZE:

The sample size comprises of sixty respondents were the customers who had an account in the Karnataka bank within Mangaluru. This study is conducted to know the awareness and the use of E- Banking services provided by Karnataka bank mangaluru.

5. LITERATURE REVIEW:

According to **Nagesh G Shirodkar (2012)** banks do not compensate the customers on account of gross negligence on the part of the customers. E-banking is latest emerging trend in the Indian Banking scenario. Prior to liberalization of banking system, the usage of banking system was restricted to foreign banks. The banking sector in India has made remarkable progress the since economic reforms in 1991. Customers are more becoming conscious about their rights and demanding more services ever than before. Better service quality, innovative products, better bargains are the needs of the customers.

According to **Ram Kumar Sinha (2011)** E-banking is defined as the automated delivery of new and traditional banking products and services directly through customers through electronic, interactive communication channels. A debit card is meant for those who desire to control spending on shopping within a specified budget. A debit cards is suited for middle income account holders. Debit card allows you to spend only what is in your account. It is easier to obtain a debit card, as compared to a credit card. While travelling to abroad there is no need of carrying stocks of cash. Today most of the debit cards are globally valid. The card can be used till the last working day of the month indicated on the card after which it expires.

Barbara R. Lewis, Kurt E. Hoel, (1993) , The banking environment is characterized by continuing social, economic, technological and regulatory change, and current challenges include increasing competition from both bank and non-bank institutions, rapidly developing technological innovation, and changing customer needs. The focus is on technological developments and the Nordic Bank environment, and findings from a survey among Norwegian companies are presented. The Survey considers their use of and attitudes towards electronic banking services. Recommendations are made with respect to the marketing activities of Norwegian banks with regard to electronic cash management services for corporate clients, and the future for such services.

Van Hoeck, (2001) .With cyber cafes and kiosks springing up in different cities access to the Net is going to be easy. Internet banking (also referred as e banking) is the latest in this series of technological wonders in the recent past involving use of Internet for delivery of banking products & services. E-business has been continuously growing as a new industry during the last decade in the wake of the internet revolution, electronic commerce emerged and allowed businesses to interact more effectively with their customers and other corporations. In this proliferated information age, banking industry has been using this new communication channel to reach its varieties of customers.

Diniz(1998) in his view states that Electronic banking encompasses a broad range of established and emerging technologies. Some are “front end” products and services that consumers opt for, such as ATM cards and computer banking; others are “back end” technologies used by financial institutions, merchants, and other service providers to process transactions, such as electronic check conversion. Some are tied to a consumer bank account; others are unrelated to a bank account but instead store monetary value in a database or directly on a card. It is the types of services through which bank customers can request information and carry out most retail banking services such as balance reporting, inter-account transfers, bill-payment, etc., via telecommunication network without leaving their home /organization.

Carmel Herington, Scott Weaven, (2009) in this paper explores the measurement of e-service quality for e-retail banking, the importance of e- service quality dimensions to e-retail bank customers, and the relationship between eservice quality and customer satisfaction. This paper informs knowledge gaps related to the measurement and structure of e-service quality, its importance and impact on customer satisfaction. A more holistic measure of e-service quality is supported. Good e-service performance impacts customer satisfaction positively, but does not override unsatisfactory performance in other areas.

6. ANALYSIS OF SURVEY DATA:

Table no 1: Showing the reasons for banking with Karnataka Bank.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage
Nearest branch	30	50
Quality of service	20	33
Cost of service	3	5
Security	7	12
Technology product	0	0
Total	60	100

Table no2: Showing Customers’ satisfaction in relation to E- Banking services.

Particular	No of respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	8	13
Satisfied	37	62
Neutral	14	23
Dissatisfied	0	0
Highly dissatisfied	1	2
Total	60	100

Table no 3: Showing Customer’s awareness about E- Banking services.

Particulars	No of respondents
Debit card/ ATM	60
Internet banking	29
Mobile banking /KBL mobile plus	35
SMS Banking	33
E passbook/ KBL m Passbook	10
E purse	3
NEFT/RTGS	18

Table no 4: Showing users of various E- Banking services provided by bank.

Particulars	No of respondents
Debit card/ ATM	56
Internet banking	15
Mobile banking	20
SMS Banking	24
E passbook	7
E purse	1
NEFT/RTGS	10

Table no 5: Showing various transactions for which debit cards are used.

Particulars	No of respondents
ATM-cash withdrawal	56
ATM-Prepaid mobile recharge	20
ATM- Fund transfer	14
ATM- shopping at merchant	36
Online shopping	27

Table no 6: Showing reasons for not using debit card for shopping at merchant.

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
I'm not aware of this facility	2	8
I'm scared to use	10	42
I prefer to pay by cash	12	50
Others	0	0
Total	24	100

N=24 total no of respondents are not using card for shopping at merchant

Table no 7: Showing reasons for not using debit card online shopping.

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
I'm not aware of this facility	2	6
I'm scared to use	8	24
I prefer to pay by cash	19	58
I'm worried about additional charges	3	9
I don't know where it can be used	1	3
Total	33	100

N=33 are the number of respondents who are not using debit card for online shopping.

Table no 8: Showing reasons for not using internet banking.

Particulars	No. of respondents
I'm not aware of this facility	4
I'm scared to use	8
I prefer to pay by cash	18
I'm worried about additional charges	11
I'm facing difficulty with internet connectivity	5
Not applicable since I'm already using	15

Table no 9: Showing reasons for not using mobile banking.

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
I'm not aware of this facility	4	10
I'm scared to use	7	18
I prefer to pay by cash	16	40
I'm worried about additional charges	9	22
I don't have smart phone	4	10
Total	40	100

N=40 are the no of respondents who are not using mobile banking.

Table no 10: Showing reasons for not using SMS banking.

Particulars	No. of respondents	percentage
I'm not aware of this facility	14	39
I'm scared to use	6	17
I'm worried about additional charges	8	22
I don't know how to operate phone	4	11
I don't have smart phone	4	11
Total	36	100

N=36 are the no of respondents who are not using SMS banking.

Table no 11: Showing reasons for not using E passbook.

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
I'm not aware of this facility	24	45
I'm scared to use	1	2
I'm worried about how to operate	15	28
I don't have smart phone	11	21
I'm worried about additional charges	2	4
Total	53	100

N=53 are the non users of E passbook.

Table no 12: Reasons for not using NEFT/RTGS.

Particulars	No .of respondents
I'm not aware of this facility	15
I prefer to pay by cheque	15
I'm worried about additional charges	9
I don't know where it can be used	7
I'm facing difficulty with internet connectivity	4

Table no 13: Showing benefits to customer's while using E- Banking services.

Particulars	No. of respondents
24*7 convenience	30
Inexpensive	8
Easy to use	20
Easy fund transfer	6
Others	1

Table no 14: Showing users of internet and mobile banking in a month.

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
1-2 times	13	54
3-5 times	9	38
6-10 times	2	8
More than 10 times	0	0
Total	24	100

N=24 are the users of internet and mobile banking in a month.

Table no 15: Showing users of KBL E-passbook in a month.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage
1-2 times	2	29
3-5 times	2	29
6-10 times	2	29
More than 10 times	1	13
Total	7	100

N=7 number of customers who use Corp e passbook.

Table no 16: Showing users of NEFT/RTGS in a month.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage
1-2 times	5	46
3-5 times	4	36
6-10 times	0	0
More than 10 times	1	9
0 times	1	9
Total	11	100

N=11 number of users of NEFT/RTGS.

Table no 17: Showing users of debit card for ATM transactions in a month.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage
0 times	1	2
1-2 times	27	48
3-5 times	17	30
6-10 times	8	14
More than 10 times	3	5
Total	56	100

Table no 18: Showing users of debit card for shopping transactions.

Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage
0 times	1	3
1-2 times	21	58
3-5 times	12	33
6-10 times	2	6
More than 10 times	0	0
Total	36	100

N=36 are the users of debit card for shopping transactions at shops in a month.

Table no 19: Showing users of debit card for online shopping.

Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
0 times	3	11
1-2 times	18	66

3-5 times	5	18
6-10 times	1	4
More than ten times	0	0
Total	27	100

Table no 20: Showing mode of payment preferred by the customers.

Particulars	No. of respondents
Cheque	8
Internet banking	5
Cash	35
Debit card	26
NEFT/RTGS	1

Findings:

- From the above study it is clear that people prefer location of the branch criteria for banking with particular bank.
- Majority of the customers are satisfied with the services provided by the bank which indicates that good customer service is provided by staff.
- Debit card is most popular technology product of the bank with 100% of the respondents being aware of the facility.
- The Karnataka Bank provides various E- Banking services. The customers of Karnataka Bank mostly avail the benefits of debit card/ATM.
- The customers use ATM card for cash withdrawal in large number the main reason behind this is ATM machines are very easy to operate and it can be easily understood by the common man. Number of people using debit card for ATM usage is nearly twice of those using it for shopping transaction like at supermarket, petrol, mall and online transactions.
- The majority of the customers prefer to pay by cash instead of using debit card for shopping at merchant.
- The customers of Karnataka Bank prefer to pay by cash on delivery instead of using debit card for online shopping.. Few of the respondents were scared to use the card for shopping due to security reasons.
- The customers of Karnataka Bank prefer to pay by cash this is considered as one of the main reason by the customer for not using internet banking.
- The customers of Karnataka Bank prefer to pay by cash. It is one of the main reasons by the customer for not using mobile banking.
- Most of the customers of the Karnataka Bank are not aware of SMS banking facility. So this is one of the main reasons for not opting to SMS banking. Majority of the bank customers are not availing SMS banking facility at bank charges.
- 45% of the customers are unaware of the E passbook and 28% of the customers are worried about the operating system.
- Usage of NEFT/RTGS is low because people prefer to pay by cheque and some of them are not aware of this facility.
- Round the clock banking convenience and ease of use are the primary factors responsible for customer's adopting E- Banking facility.
- Out of 60 customers 36 of them don't use internet banking and mobile banking even once during the month.

- Out of 60 customers 53 of them don't use KBL e passbook even once during the month.
- Majority of the bank customers still prefer the traditional passbook and have not migrated to e passbook.
- Usage of RTGS/NEFT is low because in a month people prefer to pay by cheque and cash. Hence not adopted E- Banking channels like NEFT/RTGS.
- Most of the respondents use debit card for ATM withdrawal it is clear that they prefer cash over cashless transactions.
- 58% of the customers shop for 1-2 times in a month using ATM card for shopping transactions.
- Out of 60 customers only 27 of the customers use debit card for online transactions. 66% of them customers use debit card for online transactions.
- 35 of the customers prefer to pay by cash. 26 of them also prefer to pay by debit card on an average.

Suggestions:

- Bank should aggressively market its technology product so as to educate its customers on the uses of technology product and then enjoy its conveniences.
- Bank has to focus its marketing efforts in creating awareness of E passbook and E purse which will have very low awareness.
- Since shopping transactions results in income to the bank, bank needs to run discount campaign and provide offer so as to encourage spend at supermarket and online shopping
- Few of the respondents scared to use the card for shopping due to security reasons.
- Bank needs to migrate the customers from cash to cashless transaction through various customer outreach programs. Bank also needs to educate the customers on the security aspect of the card usage.
- India is still a cash based economy and lot of thrust has to be given for digital transactions. Customers are scared of service charges that bank may levy service charges based on usage.
- Since mobile banking and internet banking are provided free of service charge by Karnataka Bank, the bank staff should market these products by communicating that these facilities are provided free of charge by the bank.
- Bank can explore the possibility of reducing charge or debiting quarterly instead of annual charge.
- Bank needs to identify the customers who are not using internet banking and mobile banking and send SMS alerts to these customers to use the products.
- Whenever customers approaches the bank to update the passbook the branch staff should encourage the customers to download the E passbook and hand holding them
- Since the bank incurs the cost in the maintenance of ATM infrastructure. Migrating the customers to cashless transactions like shopping super market using debit cards, internet banking and mobile banking will improve the profitability of the bank.
- Demonetization move after government is to encourage cashless transactions and Karnataka Bank has to make every effort by migrating the customer to digital transactions which will not only provide 24*7 conveniences to the customers but also improve profitability of the bank.

Conclusion:

The basic objective of research was to analyze the awareness among the customers of Karnataka Bank, Mangalore. Although the findings reveal that people know about the services but still many people are unaware and many of them are hesitant to use the services due to various reasons. The bank should promote its digital products so that more and more of its customers start using E- Banking products and thereby reduce the pressure on the branch counter. The migration of customer to E- Banking shall enable the branch staff to concentrate more on business development and there by improve the performance of the branch. The adoption of E- Banking services by the customers will enable to access the banking services 24*7 and thereby enjoy the convenience of banking from home or office. The bank should also explore the possibility of promoting its digital products through the various social media platform which are extensively used by the youth. It is evident that Karnataka Bank has full range of E- Banking products however the same are not fully utilized by the customers. It is widely believed that technology will play pivotal role in banking in years ahead. Under these circumstances migrating the customers from branch to E- Banking products is critical for sustaining the profitability of the bank.

Through the demonetization initiative the government of India is also encouraging cashless transactions and the use of E- Banking channels is critical for migrating the customers from cash to cashless modes. Cashless transactions will reduce the dependence on physical cash by reducing costs associated with cash handling. Cashless transactions also help in better tax compliance for the government. As some of the respondents to the survey have expressed apprehension over the charges being levied bank can examine the possibility of reducing the charges. Wherever the services are provided free of charges, the branch staff will clearly communicate the same to the customers and thereby facilitate marketing of E- Banking products

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Paper 3

**AGRI-TECH INNOVATION – AN OPPORTUNITY
FOR IMPROVED AGRI-PRODUCTIVITY- WITH
REFERENCE TO DAKSHINA KANNADA DISTRICT**

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Abstract:

Agriculture is one of the essential activities of the world which fulfills human basic needs and provides key ingredients to all other sectors. Despite of all this importance of agriculture, the population involved in agriculture is very small. In this fast growing world youths are not willing to do agriculture activities as they concentrate much on getting official jobs or corporate jobs which provide them handsome salaries without making the hand dirty.

A number of improvements have been made to make agriculture easier and more interesting, and innovation is the main reason behind these improvements. This study focus on the emerging technological trends and innovations developed and being marketed by agribusiness companies by taking into consideration the agricultural needs of farmers in Dakshina Kannada.

Keywords: Emerging technologies and trends, innovations, Awareness of farmers, Need of agriculture technologies, improved productivity.

1. Introduction

Modern era becoming so much of competitive. Changes are happens for every seconds. Innovation is the main reason behind these changes. Agriculture is one of the oldest and essential activities of the world. The productivity of agriculture is a must for all but the population engaging in agriculture is very less, resulting an imbalance between demand for agriculture products and its supply, which has been a detriment to the economic growth of the country. Many innovations have been implemented in agriculture to alleviate this imbalance which creates both opportunity and complexity on the part of farmers. One of them is, doing agriculture by using machineries and technologies and gets high yields from it. The use of technologies in agriculture not only easier agriculture but also increases the production of agriculture. Over the last couple of decades, there have been considerable developments in the field of agriculture technologies.

2. Review of Literature

Kute S. R. Made a Study on Impact of New Agriculture Technology on Productivity of Certain Crops in Marathwada

In this article author stated that application of machines in agriculture helping the farmers to increase the farm productivity. There are many machines and technologies are available in the market but farmers do not have the right information about them. The authors expressed the hope that the agricultural product could be enhanced by providing proper information on agriculture technologies and by providing machineries at concessional cost to buy machineries.

Kumar and Pramod Made a Study on “Economic Impact of Technology in the Development of Agriculture in Uttarkand”

Author reported that use of technologies in agriculture have been essential to meet the demands of market. But in most cases farmers are hesitant to buy machinery because of lack of funds and high cost of technology. If there are initiatives and support from the government side, the use of technologies in agriculture will increase.

S.K. Jayasuriya and R.T Shand made a study on “Technical Change and Labor Absorption in Asian Agriculture: Some Emerging Trends”

In this Article Authors stated that, Establishment of agro tech industries create more jobs for the youth which is considered to be one of the alternative solutions for unemployment problem in Asia. These agro tech Industries provide machinery for farmers; causing not only to increase agricultural productivity but also reduce costs and manpower, resulting in less use of personal in agriculture, which again has a negative impact on employment.

Anne Mime Adrian, Shannon.H.Norwood, Paul L.Mask Made a Study on “Producers’ Perceptions and Attitudes toward Precision Agriculture Technologies”

The authors reported that the pattern of farmers’ attitude towards agricultural technologies. Farmers are using technology to gain economic benefits such as increasing production, reducing costs and effort. The level of literacy of farmers contributes positively to the adoption of agricultural technologies.

C.H Hanumanth Rao Made a Study on “Technological Change in Indian Agriculture: Emerging Trends and Prospective”

After Green revolution there is considerable improvement in the Production of food grain with the application of technology in agriculture. Applications of technology in agriculture have the advantage of land and labor saving which will reduce the overall cost of agriculture activities. In India still for some extent, small rural farmer hesitant to purchase agriculture technologies because of high cost of machinery that imposed from some multinational companies. In the end, the authors suggested that in order to solve the problem, the government would need to undertake some plans and schemes to proper deliver of technology to the rural poor farmers.

3. Need of Study

Agriculture means not a one man activity; more manpower and time are needed to manage agricultural crops and carry out agro-related activities. In the earlier days most of the families in the district were under joint family system, so most of the agriculture activities were exclusively done by family members only. Unfortunately with time changes the joint family has diminished and this has adversely effecting on agriculture development. Non availability of agriculture labours creates headache on the landlord to carry out their traditional occupation properly. In Dakshina Kannada it was showing that many people left agriculture because of labour issue. This issue can be resolved with the use of technology, as technology requires less labours and anybody who knows the technology can easily operate it. However some of the constraints restricted the farmers from using these new technologies such as high cost, lack of awareness, illiteracy, etc.

4. Objective of the study

1. To know the emerging technologies in the district.
2. To examine is technologies really helping farmers to improve agricultural productivity.

3. To study the awareness of farmers about the technological innovation developed by agribusiness companies.
4. To evaluate whether technologies are really available to poor farmers at affordable prices.

5. Scope of study

The present study is about emerging technological trends in agribusiness and its role to improve agriculture productivity by the farmers in Dakshina Kannada district.

6. Methodology

The study is undertaken in the Dakshina Kannada district. For this study secondary source of data was used. Secondary will be collected from the Krishi Samparka Kendra officer in Mangaluru, by consulting SKADS outlet Bunder, Mangaluru, and by referring various news papers, Publications, Articles.

7. Agriculture in Dakshina Kannada an overview

In Dakshina Kannada Once upon a time agriculture which was regarded as the basic activity of the people living here. But due to some reasons people are losing interest in agriculture and they are interesting towards some other non agriculture activities. Still some are inevitably doing farming in order to continue their traditional occupation and provide for the needs of their families. Total geographical area of the district is 4771 sq.kms. The district is characterised by high rainfall and high humidity in nature. Soils of this location is identified as lateritic and acidic in nature which are rich in iron contents and have less fertility as compared with other soil type. Due to the soil quality of the area, only a few crops are suitable to grow here, those are, Paddy, Wheat, Pulses, tea, Coffee, Rubber, Coconut, Cashew, and Areca nut, Black Pepper. The net sown area consists of 28% of the geographical area. Major agriculture activities of this region includes growing food and commercial crops, dairy farming, horticulture etc.. Major agriculture products of the region include Coconut, Rubber, Paddy, Areca nut, and Cashew, Cocoa and Black Pepper.

8. Need of technology in agriculture

In the past, traditional plow and some traditional methods have been adopted in agriculture but in the current era, agriculture has changed. The modern age creates a situation where either must adopt technology in agriculture or quit agriculture. Technology considered being very essential in agriculture due to following:

- High crop productivity
- Easier the work
- Time saving
- Reduces the problem of unavailability of labour
- Cost saving
- Proper utilisation of available resources

Emerging agriculture technologies in Dakshina Kannada identified as under they are:

1. Power tiller

Power tillers are considered essential nowadays, which minimizes the problems associated with the handling of bull carts required for land plowing. Power tillers have been introduced to handle major agricultural activities. It will perform most of the farming tasks such as farming, sowing, weeding and so on. The machine consists a separate blade for weeding. It is

widely useful in paddy cultivation. Cost of the tiller ranging from 11 thousand to 3 lakh which is differs from machine to machine depending upon the characteristics of the machine. In Dakshina Kannada even small or marginal farmers are demanding for power that ranging from 12 H.P to 18 H.P. because easy to use and less cost compared to tractors or paddy cutting machines. Main advantages of this: Easy to use, Less cost, Availability of supporting schemes

2. Areca nut peeler or Areca nut Dehusking

These machines are operated with the help of electricity. On the top of machine it consists one storage part there one have to insert the areca nut after the process of dehusking kernels and husk flow to duct. In the later stages, the kernels have been thrown out from machine and the seeds are stored in the machine. The cost of the machine around 25 thousand now concessional financing also available to the farmers.

3. Pepper decorator

This machine has been introduced to separate and cleans the pepper. To separate and clean the pepper human will take many hours. Chances of getting some pains and hurts on hands are common in the process of pepper cleaning and separation. To avoid these problems pepper decorators is an alternative method. This machine have the capacity to clean around 45-50 KGs of pepper in one hour. This machine is now available at affordable prices.

4. Grasse cutter

This machine helps the farmer to remove unwanted plants and weeds. As it is known fact that weeds and some plants are harmful to the growth of agricultural plants. This machine helping the farmers to remove weeds and plants without much waste of time. Diesel is needed to run this machine. Cost of this machine is around 20 thousand; some subsidies are also available to help the farmers to buy this machine.

5. Cow Milking Machine

Earlier farmers milk the cow by their hands only. However milking a whole herd of cow twice a day or once a day is considered to be time and energy consuming task. Moreover some reports suggested that milk cow by hands not good for cow's health. To eliminate such problems 'milking machine' has been introduced. This machine helps the farmers to milking the cows quickly and to increase the dairy products. The cost of the machine starts at Rs 17,000, which also allows farmers to get some subsidized financing from cooperatives and other government agencies.

6. Areca nut tree Climber

For harvesting the areca nut, for applying pesticides climbing the tree is essential. Manually climbing the tree is normal method in earlier days. Manual method of climbing requires skilled personnel. Now farmers are facing the problem of non availability of skilled labour to climb areca nut trees. As a solution to this problem Areca nut tree climber machines were introduced. Major advantage of this machine is anyone can climb the tree without any fear. Anyone who will not at all knowing how to climb areca tree can use this machine.

7. Areca nut tree climbing scooter

This machine has been invented by one of farmers in Dakshina Kannada; the name of innovator is Ganapathi bhat. The Machine helps the farmers to climb areca tree easily to pluck areca nuts and apply pesticides. The machine will take less than 1 minute to climb an

Areca tree. One can climb areca tree with the help of this without any pains on legs or hands. This machine has been considered as an alternative for manual areca tree climbing machine. It runs with the help of petrol. With one liter petrol machine able to climb nearly 90 trees. Major advantages of the machine identified as: Time saving, Cost saving, Efficiency and Less human effort.

8. Power Weeder

Weeds are normally harmful for the healthy growth of agricultural plants. Removing these weeds consider to be essential in agriculture. In past, the sword was used to remove weeds which require more human effort and sometimes causing for leg and back pains.

Power Weeder machine has been invented to remove weeds flexibly without much human effort.

9. Paddy Cutting Machine

Paddy harvesting requires more manpower. But now the problem of getting labour to farm activities is more. To solve labour related problem in paddy harvesting paddy cutting machine has been introduced. With the help of this machine one can easily harvests the whole paddy field with less time.

10. Rice Transplanter

As the name of the machine suggests, this machine can be used to transfer paddy seedlings into rice fields. In this machine there are two type, those are riding type and walking type. Riding type is power driven and can usually transplant six lines in one pass. On the other hand, walking type is manually driven and can usually transplant four lines in one pass. The price of this machine is high, so most of the small farmers preferring to get rental based services from the big farmers who own this machine.

11. Motor sprayer

A sprayer is equipment used to apply herbicides, pesticides, and fertilizers on agricultural crops to protect them from insects. Traditional sprayer requires at least 2 people to perform the work of applying fertilizers and other chemicals on agri crops. With the use of this machine only one person can applying medicines on plants without much effort. The Cost of this stating from 2000.

12. Mini tractors

This is an alternative option for oxen. It efficiently manages the work with minimal human effort and low cost. This will help prepare the ground for sowing. This product is highly demandable by the consumers in Dakshina Kannada because the price of the machine is reasonable and the farmers can get supporting financing to buy the product.

Price of the machine raging starting from 9 thousand to 20 thousand, availability of subsidies makes the farmers to buy this product more in number.

9. Findings

- Government agencies and some cooperatives is offering subsidies and support prices to buy machinery, which is promoting rural farmers to purchase and use more technology in agriculture
- In the district, the number of farmers using machinery and technologies in agriculture has increased tremendously.
- The amount of land cultivated using technologies has increased from 20 hectare to 60 hectare.

10. Conclusion

Now application of Technologies in agriculture is very much needed to increase productivity to meeting the excess demands of the market. Technology uses means that normally requires awareness of technology, but due to some issues farmers not getting proper information about the machines such as availability, cost, support price and subsidies etc which are restricting farmers from using technologies in agriculture. Subsidies and support prices are not only enough to promote the use of technology in agriculture, but also need to communicate all the necessary information on technologies in a timely manner so that we can get better yields from agriculture in the future.

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Paper 4**E BANKING****Ravisha B.*, Reema Agnes Frank**, Meghana Prabhu S.*****

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Abstract:

Today, banks are focusing more on customers and their satisfaction. Banks are required to give top priority in providing satisfactory and efficient service to their customers. The main objective of this study is to analyze the satisfaction level of customers towards E-banking services in Dakshina kannada region. Primary Data collected were analyzed by using frequencies and Chi Square test. The data were gathered and from the field through the questionnaires administered to make analysis. A survey was undertaken where respondents completed a questionnaire about their perceptions of the three e-banking services i.e. ATM, Mobile Banking and Internet Banking. Nowadays Information Technology modernized our life almost in every field. One of amongst some blessing of information technology is Internet Banking that brings comfort and ease for banking activities. During few years Internet Banking has developed as cost-reducing, time saving, self-served technology and convenient channel that is accessible 24x7 across the geographies. Users of Internet Banking are increasing day by day all over the world. In today's hyper competitive environment Internet Banking acts as a competitive differentiator among banks and has become a significant revenue builder.

Key words: satisfactory, convenient, time saving.

Introduction

Every day Banking activities are modernizing with newest features and updates. All the private and public sector banks are providing various e-banking services to their customers. So the Customers can use such a facilities through their Credit and Debit Cards, ATMs, Online Banking, Phone Banking & Mobile Banking also. The advent of technology has led to the evolution of E-Banking services in the Banking arena. The coming up of the Foreign Banks and Private Banks has increased the competition many folds. Due to this the Banks have started making their E-Banking portals according to the needs of the customers as much as possible. This research paper tries to focus upon the factors which the customers look for in the E-Banking portal. Research finding aims to provide the Banks with the information about the customer perception and customer needs from E-Banking the user friendly as possible. Information technology services are considered as the key driver for the changes taking place around the world. Internet banking (IB) is the latest and most innovative service and is the new trend among the consumers. The shift from the formal banking to e-banking has been a 'leap' change. This study determines the factors influencing the consumer's adoption of internet banking in India and hence investigates the influence of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and perceived risk on use of IB. It is an essential part of a bank's strategy formulation process in an emerging

economy like India. Survey based questionnaire design with empirical test was carried out. The results have supported the hypothesis. User adoption of a technology has become a crucial or significant measure of the success or effectiveness of that technology. Revolutionary development in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the past 20 years has impacted individuals as well as businesses in a profound way. Internet banking (IB) is a radical technological innovation with potential to change the structure and nature of banking. To sustain business competitiveness, more and more banks are transforming from their traditional approach of “bricks and mortar” into a “clicks and mortar” one under the recent emergence of electronic commerce and business.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To analyze the customer awareness on e banking service provided by the banks
2. To identify the factors those are inducing the customer to prefer e services.

Methodology Applied**Primary Data**

The research is developed through observation and collection of data through questionnaires. Theory is developed on the basis of field visit and result of the data analyzed.

Secondary Data

Theory is developed on the basis of referring secondary data like books, journals and magazines.

Sample Size :

The sample size is determined as 60 respondent's opinion from the customers of ICICI, HDFC, AXIS, SBI, VIJAYA BANK and CANARA BANK from in and around of Mangalore.

Statistical tool:

To analyze the data X^2 technique is used and arrived conclusion from this analysis.

Internet Banking

IB is the latest in the series of technological wonders of the recent past. ATMs, Tele-Banking, Internet Banking, Credit Cards and Debit Cards have emerged as effective delivery channels for traditional banking products. Banks know that the Internet opens up new horizons for them and moves them from local to global frontiers. IB refers to systems that enable bank customers to get access to their accounts and general information on bank products and services through the use of bank's website, without the intervention or inconvenience of sending letters, faxes, original signatures and telephone confirmations. It is the types of services through which bank customers can request information and carry out most retail banking services such as balance reporting, inter-account transfers, bill-payment, etc., via telecommunication network without leaving their home/organization. It provides universal connection from any location worldwide and is universally accessible from any internet linked computer. Information technology developments in the banking sector have speed up communication and transactions for clients. It is vital to extend this banking feature to clients for maximizing the advantages for both clients and service providers. Internet is the cheapest delivery channel for banking products as it allows the entity to reduce their branch networks and downsize the number of service staff. The navigability of the website is a very important part of IB because it can become one of the biggest competitive advantages of a financial entity. Bankers consider 'minimizes inconvenience', 'minimizes cost of transactions' and 'time saving' to be important benefits

and 'chances of government access', 'chances of fraud' and 'lack of information security' to be vital risks associated with electronic banking. Due to increase in technology usage the banking sector's performance increases day by day. IB is becoming the indispensable part of modern day banking services.

Consumer acceptance of internet banking

Technological innovations are having significant importance in human general and professional life. This era can safely be attributed as technology revolution. The quick expansion of information technology has imbibed into the lives of millions of people. Rapid technology advancements have introduced major changes in the worldwide economic and business atmosphere. Research on consumer attitude and adoption of IB showed there are several factors predetermining the consumer's attitude towards online banking such as person's demography, motivation and behavior towards different banking technologies and individual acceptance of new technology. It has been found that consumer's attitudes toward online banking are influenced by the prior experience of computer and new technology. The adoption of IB forces consumers to consider concerns about password integrity, privacy, data encryption, hacking and the protection of personal information. IB requires perhaps the most consumer involvement, as it requires the consumer to maintain and regularly interact with additional technology (a computer and an Internet connection). Consumers who use IB use it on an ongoing basis and need to acquire a certain comfort level with the technology to keep using it.

Hackers

There are recent examples within which hackers are ready to access customer's files. This data can be Social Security numbers, driver's license numbers and account numbers sadly, this can be on the far side your management. However, banks have place several measures in situ to make sure your data is protected by mistreatment the strictest security measures.

Viruses

Viruses, that area unit created by hackers, area unit malicious code that may cause varied things to happen once it installs on a person's pc or network. Viruses will collect personal data, cause a complete drive to crash and even cause the whole network to finish off.

How Overcome Security Issues on Internet Banking.

To Secure Log-in ID and Password or PIN

Do not disclose Log-in and Password or PIN.

Do not store Password or Pin on the computer or any other places.

Change PIN regularly and avoid using easy-to-guess passwords such as names, birthdays and phone numbers. Password should be a combination of characters (uppercase and lower-case) and numbers and should be at least 6 digits in length.

V. EMPIRICAL APPROACH

Note: SA- Strongly Agree, A- Agree, N- Neutral, DA- Disagree, SD-Strongly Disagree.

PU = Public Sector Bank, PV = Private sector bank.

Table No 1. Role of internet banking at the present situation in the market.

SL No	Statements	Sector	SA	A	N	DA	SD	X ²	Accept/Reject
1	E banking saves time and cost of the customers.	PU	8	8	10	2	2	1.09	Accept
		PV	10	11	6	3	0		
2	It provides easy plat form to transfer the money from one place to another.	PU	13	13	1	2	1	.32	Accept
		PV	16	14	0	0	0		
3	We can easily take the statement of our accounts.	PU	10	14	6	0	0	.82	Accept
		PV	11	13	6	0	0		
4	Bank should introduce new invention to avoid misuse of e banking facility.	PU	15	14	1	0	0	.09	Accept
		PV	16	13	1	0	0		
5	Create awareness regarding the usage of e banking.	PU	12	16	2	0	0	.68	Accept
		PV	14	14	2	0	0		

Source: Primary Data

Note: Degrees of Freedom: 4. Value = 9.488 at 5% of level of significance.

Findings

1. Develop a better strategy in the banks to avoid misuse of the e banking facility.
2. It helps to save the time and energy of the users.

Suggestions

1. Keep your password safe.
2. Create awareness regarding the usage of the e banking facility.
3. Develop user friendly software's.

Conclusion

In a country like India, there is need for providing better and customized services to the customers. Banks must be concerned about the attitudes of customers with regard to acceptance of online banking. The importance of security and privacy for the acceptance of internet banking has to be given prior importance. The success of the e banking will always depends upon by the efficient use of users for their day today transaction.

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Paper 5
A STUDY ON STUDENTS PERCEPTION OF E-LEARNING

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Abstract:

Learning is a continuous process to understand, acquire, consolidate, and retrieve information. Nowadays E-learning is very much popular in the 21st Century. Electronic learning means using a computer to deliver part or all of the course whether it is in school part of your compulsory business training or a full distance learning course. The descriptive research design is developed for conducting the study. It is mainly based on both primary data as well as secondary data. Since e-learning is a modern method of education, it may hold a new way of hope for a better education system in Mangalore taluq making use of digitalization.

Keywords: E-learning, Smart class, PPT, Perception.

1.0 Introduction:

Learning is a continuous process to understand, acquire, consolidate, and retrieve information. Various learning processes are evolved over the centuries and the below picture briefly summarizes the evolution of learning.

PAST	PRESENT	FUTURE
Facilitator centered	Learner-centered	Learner Driven
Classroom learning	E-learning	Mobile/Social learning
Individual focus	Group focus	Community focus
Experts tell	Experts facilitates	Experts shares

1.1 What Is Exactly E-Learning?

E-learning, where learning is conducted via electronic media typically on the internet. E-learning is electronic learning this means using a computer to deliver part or all of the course whether it is in school part of your compulsory business training or a full distance learning course.

When it comes to online learning in education the model has been very straightforward up until 2000s education was in a classroom of students with a teacher who led the process. Now that affordable e-learning solution exist for both computer and internet, it only takes a good e-learning tool for education to be felicitated from virtually anywhere. E-learning offers the ability to share materials of all ability of formats such as videos, slideshows, word documents, and PDF (Portable Document Format).

1.2 Research Methodology:

The descriptive research design is developed for conducting the study. It is mainly based on both data primary data as well as secondary data. The primary data were collected from visiting the school and college, sample student interviews, questionnaires and formal and informal discussions with the students and teachers. The secondary data were collected from the website, the prospectus of school and college and data are related to Mangalore taluq.

1.3 Objective of the study:

- To understand the concept of E-learning
- To Identify the methods of E-learning
- To know the benefits of E-learning at Mangalore taluq
- To Know the Importance of E-Learning
- To provide Valuable Suggestions

1.4 Methods of E-learning:

1.4.1 Slide presentation software:-

Slide presentation software such as power point has become a vital part in learning/instructional settings, particularly in large classes. Power point can be highly effective tool to aid learning, but it not used carefully, may instead disengage students and actually hinder learning.

1.4.2 Smart class:-

Smart class is an advanced technology implementation for schools, which provide tools and other content for the students learning using latest media presentation. These classrooms are also called as digital or new media classroom.

1.4.3 Educomp:-

Came into being in around 2003, it was a paradigm shift that did what no one had thought of before bringing technology into classroom. It empowered teachers with good research mapped to curriculum digital modules which could project right in the classroom to elucidated and explain concepts.

1.4.4 TATA Smart class:-

TATA Smart class started in 1990 in an interactive system targeting schools in Mangalore taluq through innovative, interactive educational programs that address the learning exceptional students as well as average students.

1.5 Benefits of E-learning to Students:

1.5.1 No Boundaries, No Restrictions:-

Along with area restrictions, time is one of the issues that learners and teachers both have to face in learning. In the case of face-to-face learning, the location limits attendance to a group of learners who have the ability to participate in the area, and in the case of time, it limits the crowd to those who can attend at a specific time. E-learning, on the other hand, facilitates learning without having to organize when and where everyone who is interested in a course can be present.

1.5.2 More Fun:-

Designing a course in a way that makes it interactive and fun through the use of multimedia or the more recently developed methods of gamification enhances not only your engagement factor but also the relative lifetime of the course material in question.

1.5.3 Cost-Effective:-

This is directed to both learners and teachers, but there is a good chance that whatever your role you had to pay exorbitant amounts of money at some point to acquire updated versions of textbooks for school or college. While textbooks often become obsolete after a certain period of time, the need to constantly acquire new editions is not present in e-learning.

1.5.4 It Just Fits:-

As companies and organizations adopt technologies to improve the efficiency of day-to-day operations, the use of the internet becomes a necessity. As multinational corporations expand across the globe, the chances of working with people from other

countries increases, and training all those parties together is an issue that e-learning successfully addresses. And that's a great advantage of online learning.

1.6 Benefits of E-learning to Teachers:

1.6.1 A supportive community:

Teachers and e-learning establishments should encourage a strong sense of community amongst their online students. This will enable students to interact with one another and the instructors, as well as with the resources provided, making for an enhanced educational experience.

1.6.2 Clear expectations:

Students should be aware of what they will be receiving from the virtual class instruction, and both parties should know the preferred method of communication and delivery of the core curriculum. For example, a teacher may prefer to email assignments to students, while another might choose to deliver it via the e-learning site instead. Also, it's best to have clear expectations about how long each item of coursework should take to complete.

1.6.3 Asynchronous and synchronous activities:

It's important to incorporate activities that are more interactive, as well as those that require the student to brainstorm and research a topic in depth. This can be an important differentiator in a company's e-learning best practices mindset and thanks to the internet, students can now attend live virtual courses as well as complete coursework offline that can enable them to delve into a specific subject or skill set. Synchronous e-learning is online chat and videoconferencing. Any learning tool that is in real-time, such as instant messaging that allows students and teachers to ask and answer questions immediately, is synchronous. Rather than learning on their own, students who participate in synchronous learning courses are able to interact with other students and their teachers during the lesson.

1.6.4 Effective usage of available resources:

To get the most out of the online learning experience both the teacher and the student should take full advantage of the vast amount of resources that are available online. There are literally hundreds of online services that offer access to information, with Wikipedia being a prominent example. Instructors should seize the opportunity to enhance their content with online material or redirect students to additional web resources

1.7 Importance of E-Learning:

1.7.1 Consistent instructor presence:-

The value of feedback: The role of the instructor is very important in the e-learning process because it's in his hands to encourage, inspire and ensure students don't feel like they have embarked on the learning trip alone, and also because it will ensure that

students will be tracked and given proper feedback which is very important throughout the learning process. To facilitate such a relationship, Learning Management Systems offer options like instant messaging between peers, email and other tools that ensure learners and professors are but a click away from each other.

1.7.2 A streamlined and well-designed LMS (Learning management system):-

When talking about the success of an LMS, we primarily mean that we want an e-learning site that will be easy to navigate, is well-organized and contains high-quality material. Everyday tasks include the distribution of new material and sending, receiving and grading assignments. A well designed LMS will ensure that those tasks are hassle-free and that its users can easily tap into the myriad of features that are an important part of the e-learning process.

1.7.3 Content that is up to par:-

Aside from the ease and design of your LMS, the next most important thing to keep a student satisfied is the material. The role of the curriculum is to set the tone for an organization to design a successful course and offer both teachers and learners a set of guidelines. So while a system must be well designed and efficient, the quality of the content must be on par with the impression you want the LMS to make in its entirety.

1.7.4 Online tests and quizzes:-

Despite the fact that e-learning lacks the element of physical presence, tests and quizzes is still an essential part of the educational process. Through online tests and quizzes, an instructor is able to track the progress of students and assess the effectiveness of the curriculum, while at the same time students have the ability to track their own progress and improve on their skills accordingly.

1.7.5 It is also environmentally friendly:-

Going from hard-copy tests/ quizzes to offering the same capabilities online reduces the consumption of goods such as paper - especially important when the online classroom is large and growing!

1.8 Findings:-

The Study examines Students Perception of E-learning. For this study data was collected by structured survey. To have a fairly representative sampling, 100 respondents were randomly selected from Manglore Taluk who are students, Teachers and Principals of different schools and colleges. The collected data has been organised in the tabular form. Such organised data has been analysed with the help of different statistical tools like Average, percentage etc..for easy understanding of the data and for drawing meaningful conclusion.

Table 1.8.1: Percentage of respondent on student-based

Students	No. of respondent	Percentage %
Boys	57	57
Girls	43	43
Total	100	100

N=100

1.8.1: Percentage of respondent on student-based

From the above table 1.8.1, we can clearly understand that among the respondents 57% are boys and 43% are girls. It is clear that the majority of respondents are boys.

Table 1.8.2: Percentage of respondent on the basis of Occupation

Occupation	No. of respondent	Percentage %
Students	30	25
Teachers	25	30
Principal	45	45
Total	100	100

N=100

1.8.2: Percentage of respondent on the basis of Occupation

From the above data collection reveals that 25% respondent is students, 30% of respondents are teachers and 45% respond is given by the principal. Therefore majority of the respondent's occupation is principal.

Table 1.8.3: Product of E-learning

Product	No. of users
Educomp	29
PPT (Power Point Presentation)	48
Tata	10
CD (COMPACT DISC) / DVD (Digital Versatile Disc)	13
Total	100

N=100

From the above table, it is clear that more usable product of e-learning is PPT. Nearly 48% of user in Mangalore are using PPT, 29% are using Educomp, 13% are using CD/DVD, 5% are using TATA and other is also 10%. Therefore it is clear most preference is given for PPT in Mangalore taluq.

1.9 Suggestions:-

- ✓ Generally speaking, learning is expensive, takes a long time and the results can vary.
- ✓ E-learning has been trying for years now to complement the way we learn to make it more effective and measurable.
- ✓ The result now is that there are a number of tools that help create interactive courses, standardize the learning process and/or inject informal elements to otherwise formal learning processes.
- ✓ Several e-learning trends can give us a clear view of how the future of e-learning and learning tools will be shaped.

1.10 Conclusion:-

E-learning is not just a change in technology. It is part of a redefinition of how we as a species transmit knowledge, skills, and values to younger generations of workers and students

E-learning are the smart ways of learning education. It may reduce the use of paper works like printing of books, answer sheets, etc. It helps in reducing cutting trees which are used to produce paper. This may be a new trend in digital learning. Since e-learning is a modern method of education, it may hold a new way of hope for better education system in Mangalore taluq making use of digitalization.

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Paper 6

**A STUDY OF PERCEPTION OF SELF-EMPLOYED
PROFESSIONS TOWARDS GREEN BANKING
INITIATIVES ON MAJOR PUBLIC SECTOR BANKS AT
BANTWAL TALUK (D.K)**

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Abstract:

Today our society is undergoing a series of change, every customer expect better & better services from the organizations. Banking is also one such industry today which is not exempted from this. Service industry has to still transform a lot in the midst of changing trends. Taking care of esteemed customers, managing the competition, understanding the present client requirements requires lot of out of box thinking. Banking practices have been changed from traditional banking to core banking; services have been turned to be completely customized. The biggest challenge before the bankers is it has to take strong initiative taking into consideration the completely changing physical environment, depleting natural resources & on the other hand meeting the expectations of the customers. Today we are witnessing climatic change, increasing use of papers & also emission of carbon footprint. A time has come where bankers have to educate & encourage their customers to go paperless & use technological based products. This will foster convenience in transactions, save a lot of time & also reduce operational costs, moreover it will help in preserving our planet earth even for forthcoming generations. This study focuses on understanding the perception of self-employed professionals at Belthangady in Dakshina Kannada district.

Keywords: Exempted, Transform, Requirements, Esteemed, Customized & Professionals.

Introduction:

Presently sudden changes taking place in physical climatic conditions is not a good sign for the country as well as her people. This will increase heat in the atmosphere, spread epidemic diseases & will continuously have a negative impact on human health. A study conducted by a leading research firm in the world have clearly reported that the rapid cause for this abrupt climatic change is due to the destruction in our natural resources, tampering our natural ecosystems, increasing fast urbanization by cutting & clearing more than required trees(reducing greenery & increasing pollution), using more air coolers (AC) etc. The impact of this will be directly witnessed on human beings & this will lead to reduced life span of human lives, becoming victims to strong deadly epidemic diseases & also the threat to our younger generations too.

Government of India on the other side has directed the firms to take up corporate social responsibility. Coming to the part of the banks, they have a better role to play here. On one side their staffs must motivate their customers to take up paperless banking (Mobile, Internet & POS

swiping) . The transactions undertaken through paperless banking has the following advantages to the customers & these are as follows:

- This will completely reduce transaction time & the costs associated with the same.
- Reduce consumption of paper resource (Paperless) & saves our trees.
- Reduce standing in a queue in a banks waiting for your turn to get the service.
- Anytime, anywhere banking.
- Better technological education (Use of Apps).
- Increased efficiency of transactions.

Here we find that this will also help in reducing customer travel time & also consumption of additional fuel. Customers can have easy access to their transactions on time freely without hassles of paperwork. Today banks are forced to carry out research from time to time to improve their products & services, also to bring all their products in their sites. Green banking products & services are very recent in the industry but have made vast remarkable strides in the recent years. Customers find more easy & convenient to carry out their transactions by sitting in a particular place itself. Younger generations who are very much tech savvy have a taste for green banking products of the bank. Presently the following products & services are available in the banks for the convenience of their customers & these are as follows:

- 1) Green savings & current accounts.
- 2) Green Mortgages.
- 3) Green Loans.
- 4) Green credit cards.
- 5) Green Insurance
- 6) Green NRI accounts & deposits.
- 7) Green Demat accounts & other subsidiary products.

Green banking services presently offered by the banks to its customers are as follows:

- 1) E –Statements
- 2) E- cheque books
- 3) Mobile banking
- 4) Phone banking.
- 5) Miss call facility
- 6) Dedicated Relationship Managers.
- 7) Call centers for enquiry
- 8) Toll free numbers.
- 9) Bill payment services.
- 10) Mobile & DTH (Cable) recharges
- 11) Fund transfers
- 12) RTGS (Real time gross settlements)

He above services are directly offered by the banks to their customers. Presently a study conducted has witnessed that the users of these services are found more in urban areas & in the rural areas most of the customers are not even aware of these services. The common reasons for this is that

- 1) Customer’s freedom of privacy in carrying out their financial transactions may be lost as they have to depend on some one.
- 2) Fear of technical problems& transactional failures.
- 3) Theft & loss of funds.

- 4) Lack of technological awareness.
- 5) Resistance to change as they are comfortable with old age banking.

Self-employed professionals are busy in their regular business schedules on normal working days carrying out their normal business & business transactions. Once they are completely tied up at their place of operations, they have very less time to keep moving to the banks, carry out their normal transactions, and honor their financial commitments. When banks have taken paperless transaction initiatives it has been widely appreciated by the self-employed professionals. Most of them have even encouraged their fellow mates as well as their customers to use the same. In other words this has also lead to the advent of cashless transactions which will set them free from holding & carrying physical cash & giving room for unexpected risks. Banks can also reduce their printing costs. Most of the self-employed professionals at the study area (Belthangady) have installed POS (Point of Sale) machines & also downloaded mobile banking apps of their respective banks. This will benefit their business too by encouraging customers to go for additional purchases.

Objectives of the study:

This study intends to fulfill the following objectives & these are as follows

- 1) To study green banking & its benefits.
- 2) To understand the awareness level of self-employed professionals on green banking initiatives of their banks.
- 3) To study the perception & satisfaction of respondents towards green banking.
- 4) To give findings based on analysis carried out in the study.

Methodology used:

Data for this study is taken from both primary & secondary sources. Primary data is collected from questionnaire given to the respondents & also by oral interview. Secondary data is taken from Banking journals, Annual reports of the banks, Books, newspapers & related websites. The collected data is then tabulated & analyzed using Non parametric test.

Size of the sample for this study is restricted to 50 respondents at Bantwal taluk of DK district which is considered as the study area. Area covers both urban & rural locations. Method of sampling used in this study is convenient sampling. Respondents chosen are self-employed professionals running their own business. Specifically the targeted audience is 10 kirana store owners, 8 footwear dealers, 6 vegetable & fruit vendors, 12 hardware shop owners in the town, 4 bakeries & 10 mobile & electronic shop owners.

Scope of the study:

As the numbers of customers are increasing day to day & are swiftly getting aware about green banking initiatives & technology based products also, its concern for saving future resources it is very much useful to them in one or the other ways or in one or the other situations. Still it is very necessary to disseminate knowledge for all major customers especially those who are staying in the rural remote areas where technology is still beyond their reach but are experiencing negative impact of climatic change. One of the major hurdle that need to be crossed here as early as possible is power cuts, signal & network problems etc. This is the prime reason why rural population still are comfortable with traditional banking systems & are very much reluctant to accept the changes in modern banking trends. Banks should still put lot of efforts to educate them & if possible help them to undertake technology based transactions. It is possible to carry

out higher research by taking salaried class or a common man to understand about usage of green banking services. This can be done by taking larger samples & wider study area.

Limitations of the study:

This study has observed the following limitations & these are as follows:

- 1) Only fifty respondents are taken for this study, as the number of entrepreneurs is lesser.
- 2) Smaller geographical area is selected due to the paucity of time.
- 3) Data is collected from the self-employed in their deep busy schedule & a few of them after their business hours as everything has to match perfectly.
- 4) Only public sector banks are more in the study area & hence they are taken, private sector banks are not taken in this study.
- 5) Since self-employed entrepreneurs were reluctant to respond to the financial matters, questions pertaining to their business turn overs are not asked.

Data analysis

Data is analyzed from the responses given by the respondents. These responses are obtained through data collections from the questionnaires given to respondents

Table 1: Age of the respondents

Age	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
21 – 30	22	44
31 – 40	16	32
Above 41	12	24
Total	50	100

Table 2: Gender of the respondents

Gender	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	44	88
Female	06	12
Total	50	100

Table 3: Nature of business of respondents

Nature of business	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Dealer	12	24
Distributor	14	28
Trader	24	48
Total	50	100

Table 4: Present banker of respondents

Banker	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Corporation	16	32
SBI	08	16
Canara	20	40
Syndicate	04	08
Vijaya	02	04
Total	50	100

Table 5: Banking experience of respondents

Banking experience (in years)	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Less than 3	16	32
3 – 5	20	40
Above 5	14	28
Total	50	100

Table 6: Awareness of respondents on green banking

Awareness level	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly aware	30	60
Aware	20	40
Total	50	100

Table 7: Respondents purpose of green banking

Purpose	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Convenience	20	40
Environmental concern	12	24
Time and cost saving	18	36
Total	50	100

Table 8: Type of green banking transactions carried by respondents

Type	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Mobile and internet banking	35	70
POS machine	15	30
Total	50	100

Table 9: Perception rating of green banking by respondents

Perception rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	10	20
Good	14	28
Average	18	36
Satisfactory	08	16
Total	50	100

Table 10: Satisfaction level of respondents on green banking

Satisfaction level	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	14	28
Satisfied	24	48
Not satisfied	12	24
Total	50	100

Chi square test

Chi square test is used in this study to test the association of two attributes. It is given by

Chi square = $\sum (O - E)^2 / E$

Where ‘O’ is the observed frequencies and ‘E’ is the expected frequency and degree of freedom is $(r - 1) (c - 1)$. If chi square calculated is greater than chi square tabulated, null hypothesis is rejected and if chi square calculated is lesser than chi square tabulated then null hypothesis is accepted.

1) H₀: Awareness level and its purpose of usage is independent of each other

Awareness level	Purpose of using green banking			Total
	Convenience	Environmental concern	Time saving	
Highly aware	14	07	09	30
Aware	06	05	09	20
Total	20	12	18	50

Chi square calculated is 0.8963 and the table value of Chi square at degrees of freedom $(r - 1) (c - 1)$ ‘2’ is 5.991. Hence table value of Chi square is higher than calculated value. Null hypothesis is accepted.

2) H₀: Usage of green banking services and satisfaction level of respondents are independent of each another

Green banking services	Satisfaction level			Total
	Highly satisfied	Satisfied	Not satisfied	
Mobile and E-Banking	09	19	07	35
POS machine	05	05	05	15
Total	14	24	12	50

Chi square calculated is 1.954 and the table value of Chi square at degrees of freedom $(2 - 1) (3 - 1) = 2$ is 5.991. Hence table value of Chi square is higher than calculated value. Null hypothesis is accepted.

Major findings

The following are the findings of the study:

- 1) Most of the respondents are males in gender.
- 2) Respondents with banking experience of 3 – 5 years are higher in number.
- 3) 60% of the respondents are highly aware about green banking transaction.
- 4) 40% of the respondents use green banking for their convenient transactions.
- 5) 70% of the respondents use mobile banking and E-banking and the rest 30% transact through POS machine.
- 6) 36% of the respondents perceive green banking as average.
- 7) 48% of the respondents are satisfied with green banking services.
- 8) Purpose of taking up green banking and the respondents awareness level on the same are independent of one another (Chi square test).
- 9) Usage of green banking services and the satisfaction level of respondents are independent of one another. (Chi square).

Major suggestions

The following suggestions are given by the respondents which are worth considering:

- 1) Educating rural women folk and senior citizens on how to use green banking.
- 2) Awareness campaign has to be made from time to time to educate and encourage customers to opt for green banking.
- 3) Time to time incentives and rebates should be provided for any transactions carried out through green banking. This will not only motivate them but also influence other customers to go for the same.

Conclusion

Green banking initiatives are taken to save our resources as well as our forth coming generations. This will not only help the customers in carrying out their transactions with speed, efficiency and convenience but also help the bankers in increasing their customer size and volume of their business. Green banking will be the future of our Indian banking, as preferably our younger generations wants the same. They prefer to carryout banking transactions without visiting bank branches.

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www.corpbank.com

www.canbank.com

www.sbi.com.in

Paper 7

IMPACT OF DIGITAL BANKING ON RURAL CUSTOMERS – A CASE STUDY OF SYNDICATE BANK CUSTOMERS

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Abstract:

There are a lot of developments in the financial industry and new opportunities in digital developments. Today banks have welcome wireless and mobile technology into their boardroom to offer their customers, the freedom to pay bills, planning payments while stuck in traffic jams, to receive updates on the various marketing efforts while present at a party to provide more personal and intimate relationships. In this paper, we have analyzed the expectations and opinions of customers from the bank towards its digitalization service and know the buying behavior of banking customer after digitalization in banking sector. The main aim of the paper is to study the expectations of customers of Syndicate Bank. To conduct this research we were approached 50 respondents of Syndicate Bank Manipal especially from rural area. This study is to find out how the people are using online banking for purchases, problems they are facing and the changes that resulted in their buying behavior because of online banking.

Keywords: digitalization, buying behavior, online banking, mobile technology

1. INTRODUCTION:

The advent of online Business accompanied with technological innovations and globalization is constantly propelling the businesses organization to redefine their business operations in terms of value chain reengineering and restructuring business models. Along with other sectors the financial sector is also metamorphosing under the impact of competitive, regulatory, and technological forces (Jeevan, 2000). As a result financial institutions especially the banking sector is currently in a transition phase all over the world (Cronin, 1998). The latest development in marketing financial services by banks is online banking, where banks have now put themselves in the World Wide Web to take advantage of the internet's power and access to cope with the accelerating pace of change of business environment.

The internet and evolving technologies have dramatically changed the way people do everyday activities like researching, shopping and banking. The common practice before was going to a physical store to learn more about a product, canvas, and finally purchase. Now, it's possible to do everything in a few clicks using a smart device. People don't even have to leave their homes. Online Banking is also known as home banking, electronic banking, and online banking or Internet banking means web-based banking (Hertzum et al., 2004) online Banking is the product of different generations of electronic transactions. The web-based internet or online Banking is the latest of several generations of systems: Electronic Transaction Processing, Any Branch Transaction, Automated Teller Machine (ATMs), Phone Banking, PC or House Banking.

This study is to find out how the people are using online banking for purchases, problems they are facing and the changes that resulted in their buying behavior because of online banking.

2. Organisation:

Syndicate Bank Manipal, UDUPI

is a top company in the category Banks, also known for Customer Care, Nationalised Banks and much more. Banking services also include the facility of Funds Transfer to other banks through NEFT (National Electronic Funds Transfer) and Real Time Gross Settlements (RTGS).

You have to browse the home page of our website www.syndicatebank.in. From there, click on "Net Banking Login" link.

All we need to access the Internet Banking facility are (a) Our customer ID (b) Our log in password and (c) Our transaction password.

To enable the customers to voice their grievances or to offer some suggestions for improvement in customer service, "Customer Day" is observed at all the offices of the Bank across the organisation covering branches, Regional Offices, Corporate Office on the 15th of every month (next day, if 15th is a holiday or half-day). During 3.00 p.m. to 5.00 p.m. on this day, any customer can meet Senior/Top executives of the Bank including Chairman & Managing Director without prior appointment.

Complaint Redressal :

1. In case of any complaint, the matter shall be first brought to the notice of the concerned Branch Manager for immediate redressal.
2. If the complaint is not redressed to the satisfaction of the customer, the matter may be taken up with the Regional Manager concerned (who are the Nodal Officers for complaints at our Regional Offices) at their contact address.
3. If the complainant is still not satisfied with the responses received, he can address his complaint to the concerned Zonal Office & after that to Nodal Officer at Corporate Office Bangaluru at the address given below giving full details of the case.

How to apply for Internet banking?

We can apply on line using new user option in <https://www.syndonline.in/B001/ENULogin.jsp> or Download the Internet Banking application from our website www.syndicatebank.in and submit it to your branch. The Instant Login password for the new version of Internet Banking will be issued by the branch, activated and then you can start using the Login password from the next day.

SYND CARD SERVICES

Synd Credit Cards, Synd Prepaid/Multi Currency Cards

Synd Debit Cards, Synd Card Security

(Source: www.syndicatebank.in)

3. OBJECTIVE OF STUDY:

1. To study the buying behavior of rural banking customers after digitalization in banking sector.
2. To study the factor that influence customers in adoption of digital banking.
3. To know the risk and challenges faced by customer in use of digital banking.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The aim of this paper is to find whether the buying behavior of banking customers were increased or decreased after digitalization in banking sector. In order to conduct the research a structured questionnaire was sent to 50 customers of Syndicate Bank. Out of this all responses of respondents were accepted.

Primary Data: The sources of primary data for this study were banking customers in and around Manipal

Secondary Data: Information are collected from books and journals and various websites

5. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Bamasak [4] carried out study in Saudi Arabia found that there is a bright future for m-payment. Security of mobile payment transactions and the unauthorized use of mobile phones to make a payment were found to be of great concerns to the mobile phone users. Security and privacy were the major concerns for the consumers which affect the adoption of digital payment solutions [5]. Doan [6] illustrated the adoption of mobile wallet among consumers in Finland as only at the beginning stages of the Innovation-Decision Process.

Doing payments via mobile phones has been in use for many years and is now set to explode [7]. Also mobiles are increasingly being used by consumers for making payments. "Digital Wallet" has become a part of consumers which are nothing but smart phones which can function as leather wallets [6]. Digital wallet offered many benefits while transferring money such as convenience, security and affordability [8]. Growth in technology has opened many modes of payments through which consumers can do transactions which are more convenient, accessible and acceptable [9-11], consumers have an inclination towards mobile payment apps usage [12]. Offering various benefits such as flexi payment digital wallet brands are providing extra convenience to consumers [13]. Major factor in adoption of digital wallet is convenience in buying products online without physically going from one location to another location [14]. There has been many studies conducted in past on mobile payment application to find consumer interest and they found consumer has positive inclination for the same [12].

The factors such as perceived ease of use, expressiveness and trust affect adoption of digital wallet as payment method. These factors are termed as facilitators and plays crucial role in adoption of digital payment solution [15]. Usage of digital wallet among youth in the state of Punjab was found to be associated with societal influence and usefulness, controllability and security, and need for performance enhancement. Premium pricing, complexity, a lack of critical mass, and perceived risks are the barriers to adoption of digital payment systems [16]. A comprehensive model 'Payment Mode Influencing Consumer Purchase Model' was proposed by Braga and Mazzon. This model considered factors such as temporal orientation and separation, self-control and pain of payment constructs for digital wallet as a new payment mode. Consumer perspective of mobile payments and mobile payment technologies are two most important factors of mobile payments research [7]. Mallat [17] studied consumer adoption of mobile payments in Finland. Study found that mobile payment is dynamic and its adoption depends on lack of other payments methods and certain situational factors.

Digital wallet payments bring extra convenience to shoppers by offering flexible payment additions and accelerating exchanges [13]. Shin and Zideman [18] tested a comprehensive model of consumer acceptance in the context of mobile payment. It used the unified theory of

acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) model with constructs of security, trust, social influence, and self-efficacy. The model confirmed the classical role of technology acceptance factors (i.e., perceived to users' attitude), the results also showed that users' attitudes and intentions are influenced by perceived security and trust. In the extended model, the moderating effects of demographics on the relations among the variables were found to be significant. Digital wallets offer the consumers the convenience of payments without swiping their debit or credit cards. Instant Cash availability and renders seamless mobility is also a unique feature of these digital apps, for instance the balance in your Paytm wallet can be very easily transferred to your bank account as and when you want.

As per Ministry of Finance Report (December 2016) on Digital payment, financial inclusion is one of the foremost challenge facing India. 53 percent of India population had access to formal financial services. In this context, digital payment can act as accelerator to financial inclusion [19]. Increasing availability of mobile phone, availability of data network infrastructure, rollout of 3G and 4G networks and large merchant eco system are the critical enablers of digital payment in India. It is further supported by the coordinated efforts of industry, regulator and government. As per RBI's report 'Vision 2018' four pronged strategy focusing on regulation, robust infrastructure, effective supervisory mechanism and customer centricity has been adopted to push adoption of digital payment in India [19].

The percentage of cash for transactions has seen a rapid decline in the past few years in India. In 2010, the percentage of cash in all payments was 89% compared with 78% in 2015. This rapid decline is a result of an increased adoption of non-cash instruments such as cards and digital payments such as mobile wallets, electronic transfers, etc. Stored value instruments like mobile wallets (Paytm, Mobikwik, Citrus, etc.) and prepaid and gift cards have made payments through internet devices convenient and easy. India represents one of the largest market opportunities for digital payments. With a population of 1.25 billion, India accounts for roughly 18% of the global population. The two key drivers of digital payments-mobile phones and internet users are already well established in India. To date, India has about 1.0 billion mobile phone subscribers and 300 million internet users, ranking 2nd on both metrics globally [20].

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Respondent's profile

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Male	30	60%
Female	20	40%
Total	50	100%

(Source: Survey)

2. Age

Age	Number of Respondents	Percentage
18-25	20	40%
25-30	10	20%
30-35	15	30%
35-40	05	10%
Total	50	100%

(Source: Survey)

3. Do you use digital banking?

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	40	80%
No	10	20%

(Source:Survey)

According to the responses collected from the respondents nearly 80% of respondents are using digital banking. Remaining 20% are not using digital banking.

4. Through which customers aware of digital banking.

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Directly from bank	20	43%
Relatives and friends	05	36%
Social media	15	19%

(Source: Survey)

From the above details we can conclude that most of the users of digital banking aware by directly from bank, social media.

5. Customers' opinion while transacting in digital banking.

Particulars	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Easy	10	20%
Comfortable	20	40%
Better than normal system	05	10%
Quick	05	10%

(Source: Survey)

According to the survey 40% of respondents opine that digital banking is comfortable. 20% of respondents say that the digital banking is easy to transact. 10% respondents say that the digital banking is better than normal system and the remaining opine that it is quick to use.

6. Are all facilities of online banking available in rural area?

Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage
Yes	35	70 %
No	05	10 %

(Source: Survey)

From the above table 70% respondents are having online payment facilities in their area. 10% of respondents are not having online payment facilities in their area.

5. Preferred modes of online payments for purchasing:

Modes	No. of respondents	Percentage
Mobile banking	20	40%
Internet Banking	10	20%
Debit cards	10	20%
Credit cards	10	20%

(Source: Survey)

According to the survey majority of respondents prefer mobile banking for making payments. Around 40% of respondents use debit and credit cards.

6. Perception about risk.

Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage
High	10	20 %
Moderate	20	40 %
Low	08	16 %
Nil	02	04 %

(Source: Survey)

The above data shows that nearly 40% respondents felt moderate. 20 % respondents are felt high risk and low risk. According to data only 4 % respondents felt that the risk in online payment is nil.

7. Do respondents face any problem while making payment for purchase?

particulars	Number of respondents	percentage
yes	30	60 %
no	10	20 %

(Source: Survey)

According to the survey 20 % of respondents have faced problems while making payment for purchase. But majority of respondents have not faced any problem yet.

8. Problems faced.

particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage
Risky	2	7%
Risk of identity theft	4	14%
Technical problems	22	79%

(Source: Survey)

According to the survey majority of the respondents faced technical problems.

9. How digitalization in banking impact on your buying behavior?

particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage
Purchasing habit increases	32	64%
Purchasing habit decreases	08	16%

(Source: Survey)

In the above table we can see that 64% respondents opine that digitalization in banking will increasing the purchasing habit. Only 16% respondents say that digitalization in banking will decreasing the purchasing habit.

10. If purchasing habit increases, reasons. (80%)

Particulars	Number of respondents	percentage
It saves time	20	40%
Easy to buy	10	20%
Online banking offers discount on purchase	15	30%
No need to carry huge amount	05	10%

(Source: Survey)

According to 40% of respondents their purchasing habit has increased because online banking saves time. Around 30% of respondents have given the reason that online banking offers discount on purchase.

11. Reasons for not using online banking: (40%)

Particulars	Number of respondents	Percentage
Risky	10	20%
No necessity was aroused	04	08%
Technical problems	05	10%
Online payment services are not available	01	02%

(Source: Survey)

Out of 40 respondents around 04 respondents say that there was no necessity for them to use online banking while purchasing.

7. MAJOR FINDINGS:

1. From this study we found that most of banking customers are using online banking and they feel it's comfortable than normal system. Some are not using because till now they did not find any necessity to use and they feel it is risky.
2. Customers are having positive opinion about all facilities of digital banking availability in rural area.
3. From this study we can say that customers' opinion about risk in online banking is moderate.
4. While transacting in online banking most of the users are facing technical problems.
5. Finally from this research we found that buying behavior of banking customers after digitalization is increased.

8. SUGGESTIONS:

Here are a few ideas to be considered for encouraging digital banking:

1. Marketing and promotional programs should be conducted to create awareness among non users of online banking.
2. Banks should be very strong in the field of digital technology.
3. Taking some action to create availability of all facilities of digital banking in rural area.
4. Banks should provide more security to the money of its customers.

9. CONCLUSION:

Present study has made an attempt to understand buying behavior of banking customers after digitalization in banking sector. From this research we can see that 80 % are using digital banking and 20% are not using digital banking. Most of banking customers are using online banking for their comfort. Some are not using because they did not find any necessity to use it and they felt it is risky. Those who are using online banking are facing some technical problems while using Digital banking. Finally we can say that most of the banking customers' opinion is , after digitalization in banking sector buying behavior of customer is increased because It saves time, easy to buy, online banking offers discount on purchase and no need to carry huge amount.

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Paper 8

**PRODUCT INNOVATIONS IN THE GENERAL
INSURANCE SECTOR IN INDIA IN THE POST
LIBERALISATION PERIOD**

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Abstract

Innovations helps in business success and this is the reason why many firms spend a considerable part of their income for research and development purposes. In a competitive business environment, the firms are always in tip toe and those firms that are successful in product innovation will introduce new products and reap maximum benefit from business. In general insurance innovations help to increase the customer base of a company and improve the efficiency, profitability and thereby enhances service quality, customer satisfaction and customer retention. The path to innovation in the Indian general insurance sector is paved with the change of the regulatory system to competitive system owing to the general insurance liberalization with global tie-ups. The main objectives of the study are to find out the various product innovations in the general insurance sector in India and to compare the product innovation of public and private general insurance companies in the post liberalization period. This study tries to touch upon various ways with which innovation has been made effective so as to make new inroads in the general insurance sector in India. The study is based on secondary data sources which include Insurance Regulatory Development Authority, insurance chronicle and various journals and books by eminent authors.

Key Words- Liberalisation- General Insurance-Innovations- Product Innovation

Introduction

Innovations helps in business success and this is the reason why many firms spend a considerable part of their income for research and development purposes. In a competitive business environment, the firms are always in tip toe and those firms that are successful in product innovation will introduce new products and reap maximum benefit from business. This is short lived as other firms in the industry will follow the process and soon introduce an identical product and, in this period, the earlier firm will come up with yet another product and generate maximum profit. Hence Schumpeter, the father of innovation in economics, explains the very basic of capitalistic form of development is innovation and his famous dictum “innovate and innovate” explains the real process of development. Laziness towards innovation according to him will lead to the demise of the capitalistic system. Generally, innovation covers two stages viz. product innovation or process innovation.

In general insurance innovations help to increase the customer base of a company and improve the efficiency, profitability and thereby enhances service quality, customer satisfaction and customer retention. The path to innovation in the Indian general insurance sector is paved with the change of the regulatory system to competitive system owing to the general insurance liberalization with global tie-ups. This has resulted in market penetration with branch networks and staff strength, service delivery, etc. and the market share of companies have made a change with the entry of private insurers. Better services together with innovations in product and also in terms of digitalization, computerization, online policy

renewal, etc. have helped the private players to increase the market of the insurance products. However, even after 17 years of liberalization and reforms, the general insurance sector in India is still in its infancy with huge market potential.

Unlike in life-insurance and standalone health-insurance where new products like whole life policy, single premium policy, unit-linked insurance, critical illness schemes, group health insurance, etc. are possible, the scope for innovations in general insurance sector in India is still vast. However, the innovations in the general insurance market are limited to a greater extent to digitalization, e-policies, etc. But what is lacking in the Indian general insurance sector is products that have high consumer preferences. Customer preference should be the major objective of innovation in the general insurance sector as presently the customers purchase insurance products as any consumer goods is by comparing the price, service and distribution channels etc.

The ease of insurance business is connected with a dialoguing process between the agents and the customers and hence the process becomes easier if it is connected with technology for availing the requisite information on the part of the clients. The idea in the general insurance technology use is to reduce the time and thereby meet the demand and requirement of the customers without any delay. It also helps to generate more revenue from the insurance business if a technology driven automating service mechanism is adopted. This is beneficial to the agents as well, as it helps to increase their business like giving more insurance policies, easy to give briefing the details to the new customers resulting in more sales to an agent.

Web based agency system helps the agents in helping the clients giving assistance like application filling, sign insurance policies and proposals and thereby helping both the agents and clients to complete the formalities of insurance without meeting the insurance personnel's in their office. Though many things have been done, still some more technology innovations are required in India for developing the growth track of the insurance sector clearly. The innovation lacunae make the general insurance sector finds difficulty in giving the exact requirement of the customer. The interesting characteristic is the difficulty of the insurance companies in meeting the expectations of the customers. Hence this study tries to explore the changes and its associated ramifications of the general insurance sector in the liberalised regime connected with product as well as technological innovations *inter alia* the growth of rural and social insurance. This is explicated in three parts..

Review of Literature

Rao and Madhavi (2007) feel a healthy competition in the Indian insurance sector and this in fact is useful to the customers as they are getting different products at lesser price and quality service. They are of the view that the public-sector companies need further improvement with product varieties and new schemes to compete with the private sector. It is suggested the need for attitude change with respect to services for survivability.

The business environment in the insurance sector India has been fast changing after liberalisation of the sector and hence it not only brings new opportunities but it also brings new challenges. The major challenges in this respect are market volatility, changing customer needs as well as structural limitations (Ayem, 2010). Kapoor (2003) suggests that product innovations, insurance education, new distributional channels and improved customer service work as major challenges of the insurance sector in India in the years to come. In order to achieve these goals, the insurance companies of India have to indulge in innovations like customer base, developing new marketing channels etc.

Sam (2005) argues that the insurance scenario in India is making a big change as more competition in the sector helps to have more products and quality services and even

better prices for the products. The issues and challenges of the insurance sector are well narrated by Krishanaveni (2005) and for this it is suggested to develop an Insurance Information Bureau (IIB) with requisite data on underwriting policies, incidents of loss, claims and insurance brand. Gupta et.al. (2007) endorse the reasons and need for opening up the insurance sector for the private companies as the Indian market is very vast with high potential and the present low insurance activities in the rural and social sectors give ample opportunity for resource mobilisation for generating employment and thereby the overall development of the country.

A comparative study of the public and private insurance companies shows that the private insurance companies attain remarkable progress. It is of the opinion that these companies bring out innovative products to suit the different requirements of the people. The competition in the sector is seemed to be beneficial to both the public and private insurers and even to the people at large (Basavanthappa and Rajanalkar, 2009; Faiz, 2008).

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the various product innovations in the general insurance sector in India.
2. To compare the product innovation of public and private general insurance companies in the post liberalization period.

Methodology

This study is descriptive in nature. The study is based on secondary data sources collected from the Annual Reports of Insurance Regulatory Development Authority, Reports of Insurance companies, various journals, research articles and websites. An attempt is made to find out the various product innovations in the general insurance sector in India in the post liberalization period. Appropriate research tools have used as per the need and type of study. The information so collected has been classified, tabulated and analysed as per the objectives of the study.

Product Innovation

Profitability is linked with many factors and in this respect product innovation is a major technique the companies try to enhance their profit and market share. It manifests in manifold methods, which in turn induce the firms to develop efficiency via improved services and flexible payment techniques so as to generate a system to survive in the competitive market through cost effectiveness. Up to 2000 insurance sector is a controlled sector and it was under the aegis of the government hence the insurance products available were limited but the situation changes with the onset of liberalisation with many private companies with joint venture have enabled to deliver a wide range of insurance products.

Several factors make the general insurance sector in India challenging and these are regulatory process, performance puzzle, immature market system and miss-selling risk. Because of competition both the public and private insurance companies are forced to reach out to the customers with customer-centric products and new mechanisms in promotion methods and distribution channels. The peculiarity of the insurance sector in India is that each insurance product is offered for identical prices hence innovation is the only way to make a difference. Still some general insurance products like fire, engineering and motor are under the ambit of IRDAI and hence is regulated by tariff. Therefore coverage, exclusions and even the terms are still under the purview of IRDAI.

A perusal of the Insurance Act of 1938 gives the picture that three items like fire, marine and miscellaneous category are only coming under the general insurance list, but this has been changed mainly to motor and health. The items coming under 'others' consist of

‘property’ or ‘casualty’ insurance. Property insurance encompasses items like building, money, securities, furniture and machinery. Marine or transit insurance covers all items of cargo by air, sea and land. Casualty or accident insurance comes in the form of motor accidents. Liability insurance is the insurance as a result of the law suits.

The items coming under product innovations in the general insurance under rare risk cover methods in India are of supply chain insurance, cyber insurance, insurance on losses due to failure of renewable energy sources, insurance against climate change, carbon emission, reputation risk, micro insurance, flight insurance, primary and reinsurance and parametric insurance. The companies have been adopting product innovations for obtaining enhanced market and premium shares. Among the many innovative methods that are available in India in the general insurance, a special one in the sector is the health insurance.

Though the general insurance sector *per se* is not innovative, the sector is in the track so as to face the enhanced competition, customer loyalty, preferences, choices of general insurers are not particularly innovative. But the increased competition, changing customer preference, loyalty and preferences make the sector to be always innovative. Innovation is a necessary aspect to keep the sustainability in terms of the company’s survival and also in keeping the customers always with the company with happiness.

An evaluation of products offered by the general insurance companies is a difficult task due to paucity of the requisite data. However, a segment-wise evaluation of Gross Director Premium of the companies is undertaken in a public-private framework. The segment-wise data for the public and private general insurance sector are worked out and the results for the period 2016-17 are compared with the 10 years data starting from 2006-07 and the CAGR for each segment and total value are computed both for the public and private general insurance companies. Table 1 shows that the share of premium of public and private companies in each segment during the period makes a big upward change.

Figure.1 shows the segment-wise percentage share of GDP for the 10 years period in comparison to 2016-17. It shows a monotonic increase in every segment in the case of premium income. However, in percentage share basis it has come down during the period. The share of fire insurance in the premium income has come down from 16.59 percent in 2006-07 to 7.44 percent in 2016-17. Marine insurance premium share has also come down during the period under review from 6.54 percent to 2.28 percent. However, there is only marginal difference in the deceleration of the percentage share for the motor insurance premium. However, the total share of health insurance has doubled from 13.33 percent to 26.95 percent and this shows an increasing share of health insurance in the total premium income. The customers, in general, now give high priority for health insurance so as to cater their healthcare emergencies and needs. Here, it is appropriate to mention that the health insurance sector has undergone drastic changes in terms of product innovation as of critical illness cover, top ups, cashless treatments and health insurance portability etc. These products have been developed by the insurers to cater the changing customer requirements and needs owing to the change in their lifestyle, increasing lifestyle ailments and critical illnesses etc. A public-private evaluation of the percentage share is shown in Figures 2 and .3. For the public insurers, the inference is similar to the overall results obtained from the analysis. However, the increase in the percentage share of the health sector is high for the public insurers considering the overall data set. The share of miscellaneous products has actually come down for the public insurers for the period 2016-17 compared to the period 2006–07.

Table .1 Segment-wise Gross Direct Premium: 2006-07 and 2016-17

Year	Fire			Marine			Motor			Health			Miscellaneous		
	Public	Private	Total	Public	Private	Total	Public	Private	Total	Public	Private	Total	Public	Private	Total
2006-2007	26091	1525.47	4132.38	1137.69	490.15	1627.84	6993.88	3702.78	10696.66	2158.65	1160.64	3319.29	3361.77	1767.53	5129.29
2016-2017	506755	4470.45	9538.01	1614.52	1302.95	2917.47	23728.58	26521.95	50250.53	20739.54	7929.23	34526.61	9068.17	13580.37	30895.72

Source: IRDA

Figure 1 Segment-wise Gross Direct Premium: 2006-07 and 2016-17

Figure .2 Segment-wise Gross Direct Premium for Public Insurance Companies: 2006-07 and 2016-17

Source: IRDA

The data on private general insurance companies show a meager increase in the percentage share of the health insurance in their total premium earnings. However, motor insurance share has increased in their premium income. Increase in the percentage share of motor insurance premium might be because the motor insurance is more mandatory. For a new vehicle, the insurance has to be taken from the vehicle dealer itself and every year the company gives periodical reminders to the customers for renewal for getting the continued proliferation from the customer. Also, the renewal process is also easy for the customers as it is an online process and also, they are given additional services like vehicle tracking and claim assistance etc.

Figure .3 Segment-wise Gross Direct Premium for Private Insurance Companies: 2006-07 and 2016-17

Source: IRDA

The CAGR for the period is shown in Table.2. The values reiterate the inferences obtained from the earlier results on percentage share changes. The growth rate of premium for fire insurance is less for the public-sector insurers, whereas the private companies exhibit a double-digit growth rate in GDP. Even though the value is less than 10 percent for both the sectors, the marine insurance premium has also grown at a higher rate from the private companies than the public insurers. The growth in premium of motor insurance is drastic and is at double digit rate both for the public and private companies. However, as is evident from the changes in percentage share, the private insurers have a comparatively impressive growth rate of 19.60 percent in comparison to 11.75 percent of the public insurance companies. As expected, the growth rate in the health insurance premium is more for the public insurers than

the private insurers (22.84 percent for public insurers and 19.09 percent for private insurers). In the miscellaneous category, the private insurance companies have a growth rate of 20.37 percent in premium income compared to 9.44 percent for the public insurance companies. Except for health insurance, in terms of premium income, the growth rate has been more for the private companies. The overall CAGR value testifies the same with public insurers having a GDP-CAGR of 12.64 percent compared to 18.08 percent for the private companies.

Table 2 CAGR for Gross Direct Premium for Public and Private General Insurance Companies during 2006-07 and 2016-17

	Fire		Marine		Motor		Health		Miscellaneous		Total	
	Public	Private	Public	Private	Public	Private	Public	Private	Public	Private	Public	Private
CAGR	6.23	10.27	3.23	9.29	11.75	19.60	22.84	19.09	9.44	20.37	12.64	18.08

Source: IRDA

The overall CAGR of public sector and private sector insurance companies are 12.66 percent and 18.08 percent respectively.

Findings of the Study

- Though the general insurance sector *per se* is not innovative in the pre-liberalised regime, the sector is in the track so as to face the enhanced competition, customer loyalty, preferences; choices of general insurers are not particularly innovative. But the increased competition, changing customer preference, loyalty and preferences make the sector to be always innovative.
- Before liberalization insurance sector is under government control. Hence the insurance products available were limited. But liberalisation of general insurance enabled private companies to deliver wide range of commodities.
- Competition leads both private and public sector general insurance companies to reach out to the customers with customer centric products.
- In India each insurance product is offered for identical prices hence innovation is the only way to make difference.
- Before liberalization the three items like fire, marine and miscellaneous insurance are only coming under the category. Now new items like supply chain insurance, cyber insurance, insurance against climatic change, carbon emission, micro insurance, flight insurance and reinsurance.
- Companies have adopting product innovation for obtaining enhanced market and premium shares.
- There is an upward trends in the share of premium of public and private sector companies in each segment.
- The share of fire insurance in the premium income has come down from 16.59% in 2006-07 to 7.44% in 2016-17.
- Marine insurance premium share also come down during the period.
- There is only a marginal difference in the percentage share of the motor insurance premium.
- The total share of health insurance has doubled from 13.33% to 26.95%. This shows the increasing share of health insurance in the total premium income. So health insurance sector has undergone drastic changes in terms of product innovation.
- Product innovation is more in the health insurance segment. The percentage share of health segment is high for the public sector insurers.

- The share of miscellaneous insurance has come down for the public insurers to the period 2016-17 compared to 2006-07.

Conclusion

Product innovation have the potential to bring better and more customized insurance coverage to more people, including those of lower income groups and bring better financial protection. The new product innovation can simplify the insurance process and bring insurance to less developed markets. It will bring wider protection and better business opportunities. Insurers know that product innovation has the potential to enhance their current business. They know that they need to innovate faster in the competitive environment due to liberalization and privatization. The coming future of general insurance business will be those who can introduce larger product innovations and make it in their business strategy.

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Paper 9

INNOVATIONS AS A KEY TO SUCCESS IN MODERN BANKING

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Abstract:

Banking sector welcomes large scope for innovations in terms process, marketing and relationship management. To gain competitive advantage over the competing banks, a bank can survive and sustain with innovative way of processing, approaching and managing. Open banking, phygitive delivery, block chains, robot advising, payments anywhere, mobile and internet banking and other more innovations in the banking sector help the banks to achieve success. This paper aims to observe the needs, types, and ways of innovations in the path of a bank's success

Keywords: Relationship managements, competitive advantage, block chain, robot advising, payments anywhere, phygitive delivery.

Motive: Increased commitment to innovation in response to consumer expectations is one of the primary findings of the [10th annual Innovation in Retail Banking report](#)

Introduction:

Innovation is a key to success in every sectors of economy. Being a prominent economic player, the banking sector welcomes innovations too. They are no longer restricted to traditional methods. Thus, to increase the business opportunities and capture the fresh market banks are resorting to innovation.

Banks are already heading towards Industry 4.0 (Automation trend), creating a bank of future, enhancing financial inclusion and facilitating the convenient and digital experience for its customers worldwide.

As part of the industry 4.0, banks are experimenting with new mobile applications and voice-enabled gadgets to enhance both delivery and customization. As technologies continue to evolve, the banking sector will continue to accelerate its investments in innovation and digital enhancements.

Major innovations in banking which have been a key to success in modern banking operations in this digitech era are as follows.

1. Expansion of Open Banking through APIs.

The regulatory bodies globally are requiring banks to enable customers to share their data securely with third parties to experience new financial services and increase competition in

the banking industry. Through Applications Programming Interfaces consumers have greater freedom and control over their banking operations

Open banking APIs accelerate innovation and collaboration, leading to expanded banking ecosystems that could include more than just financial services to make a consumer's lifestyle better.

2. Commitment to Physical and Digital Delivery

The banking companies are introducing digital only banking entities, as a lot of transactions are moving to digital channels and also to combat the high cost of a traditional branch network costs. By digital-only banking system for collecting deposits, to using digital platforms for lending, investing and speciality services, banks and financial firms are focusing on quality customer experiences and increased value for customers with these phygitive delivery systems.

3. Cardless ATM service

For the first time in the globe, BankDhofar in Oman has launched a cardless banking service for ATMs which allows customers to carry out ATM transactions easily by using only their mobile numbers. For this service, customers need to activate their mobile number through the BankDhofar call centre or their mobile banking app. Once verified, customers can go to the nearest BankDhofar ATM and insert their mobile number, one-time PIN (OTP) and the card PIN, and carry out their transaction. Cardless banking allows customers to withdraw cash, pay bills, request for cheque book, make balance inquiry, and request for a mini statement.

4. Predictive Banking

One of the most exciting innovations in 2019 is predictive banking. For the first time, the banking industry is consolidating all internal and external data and building predictive profiles of customers in real time. With rich, accurate and financially viable consumer data, financial institutions know their customers very well and are able to offer advice for the future, while increasing security and efficiency. With robo-advisors financial institutions offer 'next-best actions' with personalised solutions in real time and universal cash management solutions that address implicit needs in an integrated service. Information with figures and insights are contextually delivered with the aim of proactively changing customer's behavioural patterns.

5. Block chain

This works by using a network of computers, all of which must approve a transaction in a chain of computer code. Details of the transfer are then recorded on a public ledger for anyone on the network to see. It has huge potential for banking, where it could be used to improve the security of financial transactions, decentralized services and improve speed to market for new products. There is no shortage of use-cases and applications for block chain currently being explored by the finance community. It can be used to securely store client identities or handle cross-border payments. It could even lead to 'smart contracts' that complete trades and deals automatically. A report from Santander InnoVentures

suggests that block chain technologies could save banks as much as \$20 billion in infrastructure costs by 2022.

CONCLUSION: This paper describes the innovations and types of innovations that enable the banking sector to gear its operations for the better customer experiences and enhancement of relationships as a competitive advantage to attain success in this digitech era.

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Paper 10
**PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATIONS IN TEACHING
ENTREPRENEURSHIP**

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1. Introduction

Teaching students to be entrepreneurs poses a challenge from a pedagogical perspective. For students to become entrepreneurs they must learn how to identify and pursue opportunities that create change and result in sustainable value for society. It involves student ability to apply their knowledge about how to launch a new enterprise [Halonen et al. 2002 p.284]. Introducing entrepreneurship courses in higher education builds core competence among students, even though not all students who are exposed to entrepreneurship education would start their own venture immediately or at a later date. The question whether entrepreneurship can be taught has been a major debate in entrepreneurship research and even led to the question whether entrepreneurship can actually be learnt [Edwards & Muir 2004; Rae, 2000]. Basic outcome of this study have been the identification of different aspects in entrepreneurship education of which some are teachable with the help of classical education tools and formats, while others do not seem to be teachable in same manner. Against the background of these findings, active learning concepts were increasingly integrated into entrepreneurship education [Shepherd & Douglas, 1996]

2. HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION

Katz (2003) developed the most comprehensive chronology of entrepreneurship education. While he included economic and agricultural literature and experiences dating back to 1876, and others have touted the Harvard courses taught in 1947, the reality of entrepreneurship education as a force in business schools began in the early 1970s. USC launched the first MBA Concentration in entrepreneurship in 1971 followed by the first undergraduate concentration in 1972. From there, the field of entrepreneurship began to take root

In 1987, Zenithal & Rice reviewed some of the pioneering universities of entrepreneurship Education in America contended that education in entrepreneurship covered the entire Scope of business administration, and as such was the closest approach to the original Concept of management education available in universities at that time. With the continued Increasing fragmentation of business education into narrow specializations, they believed that the a field of study that takes a broad, integrative, pragmatic, rational approach to Business would find itself increasingly popular with those who aspire to be entrepreneurs, Managers and top executives.

Also in 1987, Ronstadt proposed that entrepreneurial programs should be designed so that potential entrepreneur is aware of barriers to initiating their entrepreneurial careers and can devise ways to overcome them. Ronstadt (1987) proposed a two-continuum model of

curricular design for Entrepreneurship education. His “structured-unstructured” continuum addressed various Methods of transferring information and expertise. Among the methods he discussed were lectures, case studies, and feasibility plans. He contended that an effective program must show students “how” to behave entrepreneurially and should also introduce them to people who might be able to facilitate their success.

Four years later, Robinson & Haynes (1991) conducted a survey of universities with enrollments of at least 10,000 students to determine the extent of the growth in entrepreneurship education. While significant growth was cited, several challenges were pointed out including:

The challenge that lies in developing existing programs and personnel, thus improving the Quality of the field. There are several obstacles that need to be overcome to facilitate the development of quality in the field.

At the heart may be the lack of good solid theoretical bases upon which to build pedagogical models and methods. Another obstacle is the lack of formal academic programs, representing a lack of commitment on the part of institutions. A third obstacle is the maintenance of student interest in the academic programs. Robinson and Haynes believed that entrepreneurship education had come a long way in the past 20 years, yet there were several weak points in the field that were identified through their research. Of primary concern is the lack of depth of most of the programs that were then started. Further growth would depend upon how new programs were integrated with and nurtured by the established entrepreneurship education system.

3. **The objectives of entrepreneurship education**

Through the identification of various objectives of entrepreneurship education, we might have a deeper understanding of educational needs as well as a more weighted choice of evaluative criteria and pedagogical techniques (Alberti, 1999).

To acquire knowledge germane to entrepreneurship

Learning of knowledge, concepts and techniques about some specific area or Discipline, related to the field of entrepreneurship

To acquire skills in the use of techniques, in the analysis of business situations and in the synthesis of action plans

This objective aims at promoting skills of analysis and synthesis in the use of knowledge about accounting, finance, marketing and general management in a holistic way

To identify and stimulate entrepreneurial drive, talent and skill

aims at increasing individuals’ awareness of new venture career possibilities and supporting them in the development of awareness about their entrepreneurial interests, capabilities and potential

To undo the risk-adverse bias of many analytical techniques

This means education on how to manage risk, reducing the bias for risk-aversion. These objectives move away from traditional business education that has a bias towards quantitative analyses and an emphasis on postponing action until all the necessary data are available.

To develop empathy and support for the unique aspects of entrepreneurship

Refers to the wish/need of some individuals to understand and learn concepts related to entrepreneurship with no intent for their direct application

To revise attitudes towards change

This objective aims at educating people on how to encourage their subordinates to innovate

To encourage new start-ups and other entrepreneurial ventures

This aims at a direct stimulus in fostering new ventures, self-employment and entrepreneurial oriented careers.

To stimulate the ‘affective socialization element

This objective refers to the inculcation of attitudes, values, psychological mindsets and strategies necessary for taking on the entrepreneurial role.

In other words, entrepreneurship education aims at building the so-called entrepreneurial competencies, which are considered as combinations of the different skills, knowledge and attitudes above listed (Fiet, 2001a). The analysis of the objectives of entrepreneurship programs introduces a deeper examination of the different audiences for entrepreneurship education.

Importance of Entrepreneurship Education

Entrepreneurship is a key driver of our economy. Wealth and a high majority of jobs are created by small businesses started by entrepreneurially minded individuals, many of whom go on to create big businesses. People exposed to entrepreneurship frequently express that they have more opportunity to exercise creative freedoms, higher self esteem, and an overall greater sense of control over their own lives. As a result, many experienced business people political leaders, economists, and educators believe that fostering a robust entrepreneurial culture will maximize individual and collective economic and social success on a local, national, and global scale. It is with this in mind that the National Standards for Entrepreneurship Education were developed: to prepare youth and adults to succeed in an entrepreneurial economy.

Entrepreneurship education is a lifelong learning process, starting as early as elementary school and progressing through all levels of education, including adult education.

The Standards and their supporting Performance Indicators are a framework for teachers to use in building appropriate objectives, learning activities, and assessments for their target audience. Using this framework, students will have: progressively more challenging educational activities; experiences that will enable them to develop the insight needed to discover and create entrepreneurial opportunities; and the expertise to successfully start and manage their own businesses to take advantage of these opportunities.

Table 1 - Teaching methods

Theoretical Discussion	
Didactic model	Learning from each other
Learning from teacher alone	Learning from each other
Passive role as listener	Learning by doing
Learning from written texts	Learning from personal exchange and

	debate
Learning from “expert” frameworks of teacher	Learning by discovering (under guidance)
Learning from feedback from one key person	Learning from reactions of many people
Learning in well organized, timetable environment	Learning in flexible, informal environment
Learning without pressure of immediate goals	Learning under pressure to achieve goals
Copying from others discouraged	Learning by borrowing from others
Mistakes feared	Mistakes learned from
Learning by notes	Learning by problems solving

Fonte: Duchéneaut, 2001: 133

By Combining Didactic Model and learning from each other we can generally classify the teaching methods into following categories.

1. Case Study
2. Group Discussion
3. Individual Presentation
4. Individual Written Report
5. Group Project
6. Formal Lectures
7. Guest Speakers
8. Action Learning
9. Seminar
10. Web-based learning
11. Video recorded lectures

4. **METHODOLOGY**

Empirical Study was conducted among 250 students of Executive M.B.A Program in the age group of 20-30 years.

5.1 Sources of Data:

Secondary Data:

Secondary data is obtained from Journals & Websites.

Primary Data:

Primary data were obtained through Questionnaires & Schedules.

All the collected Data were analyzed to form the final Conclusion.

5.2 Analysis:

Data and Information collected were analyzed by Likert Scale.

5.3 Limitations of the Study:

The Information was collected from students that may include their Perception and may not be all accurate.

6. Results & Interpretation of Data

Fig.1 % of Observations based on Teaching Methods

% of Observations

Table :2 % of Observations based on Teaching Methods

Sl.Number	Teaching Method	% of Observations
1	Group Project	30
2	Case study	20
3	Guest Speaker	15
4	Individual Presentation	12
5	Group Discussion	10
6	Action Learning	5
7	Seminar	3
8	Individual Written Report	3
9	Formal Lecture	1
10	Web-based Learning	0.5
11	Video-Recorded Lectures	0.5

7.

30% of the students have opted for Group Project as a Teaching Method.

By participating in the project, students receive exposure to the resources of the Web, developed an understanding of the various functional areas within a business and how these functions were interdependent, enhanced their electronic communication skills, and experienced the entrepreneurial behavioral, affective, and cognitive attitudes that motivate individuals to succeed in small business endeavors

20% of the students have opted for Case Study as a Teaching Method.

The case study method of teaching is quite different from the traditional lecture or class discussion. It requires substantial work before and during class by both the professors and the students. But the effectiveness of this method in other fields suggests the work is worthwhile.

15% of the students have opted for Guest Speakers from the Industry as a Teaching Method

Inviting guest speakers into classroom can be an effective means to raise issues, impart real-life experiences, and drive home a specific lesson.

12 % of the students have opted for giving Individual Presentation as a Teaching Method

Individual Presentation requires students to describe an ethical situation they encountered in the

Workplace, their relevant value systems, sources of information consulted, their role in the organization, and how they resolved the ethical situation, considering how their experiences since the time of the situation might influence analogous decision making today.

10% of the students have opted for Group Discussion as a Teaching Method

Whole Group Discussion is a modified form of classroom lecture where the focus is shared between the instructor and the students for information transfer. Typically, an instructor will stand before a class and present information for the students to learn but the students will also participate by answering questions and providing examples.

5 % of the students have opted for Action learning as a Teaching Method

Action Learning is a form of Problem-based learning, but it goes further in insisting that the problem(s) being worked on must be real, in that no one knows the answer already.

3% of the students have opted for Seminar as a Teaching Method

The seminar (despite larger numbers and generally shorter timetabling slots) is still - alongside (and usually supplementing) the lecture - a dominant pedagogic genre in English Studies. At most universities, the chances are that a large proportion of your face-to-face interaction with students will take place in seminars.

3 % of the students have opted for Individual Written Reports as a Teaching Method

Very few % of the students have opted for formal lecture, Web based learning and video recorded lecture as a Teaching method

7. Challenges for Entrepreneurship Education:

During the study the following problems were quoted by the students against Entrepreneurship.

1. Cultural Barriers

People in India are more sensitive to emotional affinity in the work place than to the work and productivity. The caste system & its series of obligations reinforced the practice of following a family occupation rather than launching a new venture.

2. Difficulties towards start-ups

Business in India is costly in terms of Time required and cost involved. There is too many rules and regulations and too much paper work involved in starting a new venture.

The absence of an appropriate Entrepreneurial climate, lack of required Infrastructural facilities and lack of access to relevant technology hinder rapid Industrial development.

3. Incomplete Entrepreneurial Education:

The students are not satisfied with the “hands-on” support of their University in the founding process because of this they are not confident, not capable and lack knowledge in starting a Business.

8. Conclusion:

Unfortunately, the present Entrepreneurship education just concentrates on related courses. Moreover, the so called Entrepreneurship courses are similar to general business courses. But general business management education has no significant influence on entrepreneurial propensity (Hostager and Decker; 1999). In Entrepreneurship education the much focus should be given on Group Projects and Case Study which means that Entrepreneurship educators should give much significance to the practice based approach in the learning organizations.

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10. **Questionnaire:**

Table:3 Rate the effectiveness of various Pedagogical methods in Teaching

Rating	1	2	3	4	5
	Rating: 5 Point Likert Scale: Preference ranging from 1(not at all) to 5 (very much) (put √ (Tick) mark in appropriate column)				
<u>Teaching Method</u>					
Case Study					
Group Discussion					
Individual presentation					
Individual written report					
Group Project					
Formal lecture					
Guest Speakers					
Action Learning					
Seminar					
Web-based learning					
Video recorded lectures					

Paper 11

**MICRO FINANCE – IMPACT OF MICRO FINANCE
INSTITUTES ON FISHERMEN’S OF BYNDOOR
TALUK OF KARNATAKA STATE**

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Abstract:

In India Fishing activities are engaged in two ways -in land fishing and Sea fishing, in land fishing is done in natural sweet water and salt water rivers and also in lacks, pounds by harvesting fish, prawns and shrimp seeds. Sea fishing is the one of the specialized area where, this specialization is derived by the Trial and error methods again which leads to death, disability etc. In sea fishing unlike inland fishing there is no need of harvesting fish seeds. Karnataka has 320 Km Long Coast line and Byndoor Taluk Covers near about 40 Km of Coastal line From Gangolli To Shiroor. Sea Fishermen’s are very often called as ‘Children’s of Sea’ and in local kannada language they were called as Mogaveeraru because earlier fishermen use to live in small islands formed by rivers which are known as mogaru and hence they got name Mogaveeraru. They are fully dependent on the sea for their livelihood up to that extent even educated, graduated person also seen in fishing. Fishing in sea is not an easy task, fishermen face lot of difficulties in fishing and economically they are poor because of the Problems like Scarcity of Fishes, Natural Calamities like Hurricanes; Low prices for the fishes, Increase in Diesel and Petrol rates, Nominal Amount of Subsidies etc, In spite of all these troubles fishermen’s have sustained economically only because of credit provided by the financial institutions. In this paper an effort has been made to know the extent of dependency of Fishermen’s on Micro Finance Institutions.

Keywords: fishermen’s, credit, micro finance institutions, sea fishing, Mogaveeraru

Introduction

Sea fishing is the one of the specialized area where, this specialization is derived by the Trial and error methods again which leads to death, disability etc .., Karnataka has 320 Km Long Coast line and Byndoor Taluk Covers near about 40 Km of Coastal line From Gangolli To Shiroor. Sea Fishermen’s are very often called as ‘Children’s of Sea’ because they are dependent upon Sea for their Livelihood and Fishing Have been practiced by them since 300 Years.

Nowadays Sea fishing is not an easy cup of tea for the fishermen’s they are facing Problems and trouble in living. They are facing Scarcity of Fishes, Natural Calamities like Hurricanes; Further Government has Introduced SEZ and CRZ policies which don’t allow constructing Houses 500 to 200 meters from High Tide Line, Usually all the fishermen’s have settled in the sea Shore. Increase in Petrol And Diesel Rates, Nominal Amount of Subsidies, Low

Amount of compensation in case of Death in Sea, No proper Loan facilities, no proper Port facilities and list goes on..

Despite of All the struggles they are somewhat sustained because of micro finance provided by the Self help Group, Primary Agricultural Societies, and other Financial Institutions.

This paper is An Outcome of an effort made to know the extent of dependency of Fishermen's on Micro Finance Institutes.

Objectives of the Study

1. To Know the Reason for taking loan and utilization by the Fishermen
2. To know about economic status of the Fishermen
3. To know Educational Background of the Fishermen
4. To know about of the extent of dependency on micro finance

Methodology

The study has been undertaken in the Coastal Region of Byndoor Taluk. The Primary Data was collected through survey and interview method; Survey was conducted among 75 respondents. Structured questionnaires were issued and data has been collected through enumerators. The secondary data has been collected from e- magazines, websites, and published papers which are relevant and related to the study.

Review of literature

Muhammad Talib Kalhoro (2017) in the study of availability of Microfinance to small scale aquaculture and fisheries in India, Bangladesh and Pakistan proved that that microfinance with convenient features is much needed for fishery folk for their sustainability. Microfinance can be taken as a tool for alleviation of poverty. South Indian Federation of Fisherman Society (SIFFS) and DHAN foundation are two key components doing best towards fisheries in India.

Vipinkumar.V. & Swathi Lekshmi.P (2012) in their A Study on Impact of Microfinance Institutions on The Coastal Indebtedness in Marine Fisheries Sector of Karnataka reviewed that microfinance institutions have contributed a lot for indebtedness and repaying capacity in motorised and traditional sectors of Karnataka state. 'Masthya' Self Help groups have brought about advancement in fishing activities and members have expressed their satisfaction about functioning of MFI. Self-help groups provide loan for repair of fishing boats, education of children, dry fishing making etc. Fishery folks have also started to save their income.

Dr.K.G.Karmakar, G.S.MehtaDr.S.K.Ghosh&Dr. P. Selvaraj analysed that in South Asia Countries fisher folk are poor and exploited by merchant and middlemen. As they cannot depend on banking credit system due to lack of collateral security, MFI are the key institutions which provide financial support to fishermen. South Indian Federation of Fishermen Societies (SIFFS) consisting of 3 tier structure provide different types of loan at concessional rate of interest and special support to fisherwomen. SHG groups plays major role in empowerment of fisherwomen.

Nikita Gopal(2012), undertook study about availability and utilisation of micro credit by traditional fisheries had mentioned that fishery folk borrow loan from MFI mainly because repayment facilities are flexible. They are dependent on both Govt MF and NGO MF. The microfinance supporting activities has contributed for increase in income level and social status of the fishery folk.

R. Narayanakumar&P. S. Swathilekshn, opined that Micro Finance Institutions (MFI) and Self-Help Groups (SHG) play very important role in marine fisheries sector. They help to reduce the level of indebtedness among marine fisher folk and easy accessibility of cheap credit. The role of MFI in development of marine fisheries sector is crucial. Indebtedness level and repayment capacity of MFI members is much better than non- members of MFI.

Statement of the study

Sea Fishermen of Byndoor taluk are poor because of their dependency on fishing; they usually fall in cash crunch even they face troubles to Run day to day activities, some of them are not having any pledge able assets and even they have they are not acceptable by the financial institutions while giving loans. It is seen in the study to some extent financial

Gender	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
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institutions like co-operatives, self help groups have been helping the fishermen by providing loans for the shorter duration.

Data Analysis

Male	69	92
Female	06	8
Total	75	100
Age Group	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
Below 30	28	37.33
30-40	17	22.66
40-50	17	22.66
50-60	08	10.66
60 and above	05	6.66
Total	75	100
Educational qualification	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
Primary	30	40
High school	28	37.33
Puc	08	10.66
Under graduation	08	10.66
Post graduation	01	1.33
Total	75	100
Involvement in Sea Fishing	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
Yes	65	86.66
No	10	13.33
Total	75	100
Nature of vehicle	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
Two wheeler	30	40
Four wheeler	01	1.33
No vehicle	44	58.66
Total	75	100
Annual Income	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
Less than 1,00,000	65	86.66
In between 1,00,000 to 2,50,000	10	13.33
Above 2,50,000	Nil	00.00
Total	75	100
Long term loans from PS banks	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
Yes	15	20
No	60	80
Total	75	100
Short term loans from PS banks	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
Yes	16	21.33
No	59	78.66
Total	75	100
Loans from co operatives and finances	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
Yes	75	100
No	00	00
Total	75	100
Institutions from which	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage

loans are availed		
Farmers co-operative Societies	06	8
Private Finances	13	17.33
Other Co-operative Societies	32	42.66
Self Help Groups	24	32
Total	75	100
Reason for availing Loans	Respondents in number	Respondents in percentage
Daily use	10	13.33
Fishing purpose	40	53.33
Vehicle	06	8
Construction of Houses	15	20
Children's education	04	5.33
Total	75	100

Table .1: consolidated table showing all the necessary data acquired from the study

Findings

1. Out of 75 respondents 92% (69 in number) of the respondents are male and 8% (6 in number) female respondents.
2. Study has also identified that involvement in undergraduates in fishing 10.66%.(8 in number) and near about 77% of the fishermen are having below high school education.
3. 86.66% of the respondents are having less than 1,00,000 income and no one is having more than 2,50,000 income. Only 14.44% of the respondents are having income between 1,00,000 and 2,50,000.
4. 86.66% of the Respondents are directly involved with sea fishing and reaming are involved in fishing related activities.
5. 40% of the Respondents have two wheelers, only one respondent is in possession of four wheeler, and remaining 58.66% of the respondents are not having possession of vehicles.
6. It is observed that 20%(15 in number) have taken loan from the public sector banks and this loan is mainly for the purpose of purchasing boats. And remaining 80% of the respondents have not availed long term loans from the public sector commercial banks.
7. It is also observed that a minute percentage (21.33%) of the respondents have taken short term loans from the Public sector commercial banks.
8. In the study it is identified there is 100% dependency on Co-operative Societies, self help groups and on private finances, all the respondents have taken loan from these institutions, for short term as well as for long term.
9. 53.33% of the Respondents have utilized loans for their occupational purpose that is fishing – to purchase boats, nets and related things. 13.33 %(10in number) have taken loan for the day to day activities.

Summary and conclusion

Sea Fishermen are basically from the poor background and they have been practicing fishing activities from past more 300 years. Sea fishing is one of the talents that is

inherited to them by their ancestors along with other properties. Sea fishermen are living in the Sea shore from many years introduction of CRZ policies by the government posed a new trouble now any individual is will not be permitted to construct house from 200 to 500 meter from the HTL. Lack of fishes, natural turbulences made difficult fishermen to live. Having many problems fishermen still have not opted to diversify their occupation, change in occupation or finding alternative source of income along with fishing may bring them out from poverty. In this study it is observed that there is highest dependency on micro financial institutions. They have taken loan multiple times for the occupational purpose, repairing the house, children's educational purpose to lead day to day life and so on..

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Paper 12

ROLE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN COMMERCE BRINGS TRANSFORMATION IN THE PERFORMANCE LEVEL OF THE STUDENTS

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Abstract

In India education has been accorded much importance since independence as it has been perceived that educational development is necessary to ensure economic and overall development of the country. Education is the one of the powerful weapon to develop the standards of the young population in the country. In India we can see that majority of the population is young generation but speaking on the percentage wise people have higher education is very minimum. Now it is the duty of us to find out what are the major causes that will hinders the young population to get higher education. Quality in higher education will build the qualitative resourceful young population to bring revolution in our country. This paper is build with an intension of to evaluate the impact of the higher education in the development part of the students. To give empirical touch as a researcher I collected 50 samples of respondents to get a clear picture about evaluation of performance of the students.

Key words: causes weapon and evaluate.

Introduction

Commerce and management stream has a sea of options and opportunities for those who want to make their career and achieve their goals in life. Students who are studying under this stream have an intellectual look towards the outside world. Commerce is like a wide tree it grown up well and branches of the tree spread near all surroundings of their and people are enjoying with its fruits.

In a general term commerce means it has spread its area like trade, banking, insurance, advertising, marketing, administrative, professionals like CA, teaching..etc. there is a lot of scope for the better employment if the students opt for the commerce. Choosing a career option mainly depends on the interest of the candidates. He has to know what his potential is and where he can best suit in the employment according to that he has to select the streams. Streams have their own option to develop their career in the job market.

As a profession, it is the duty of us to guide our students to create awareness among them these the areas of the commerce and if you want to work on the particular field means, you have to divert your thinking to that mode and build knowledge. Normally in the professional course students have to go for their project work in the companies or they have to work temporarily as an intern in some of the organization. In this case he will

come to know what type of work is going and how he has to involve in this procedure. Here senior person of the company will guide the intern regarding the various process of the company. So from this student will gain a practical knowledge about the industry which he is lagging in his academic year. This will makes the person more competent and build the confidence in work.

Objectives of the study:

- 1) To analyse the career option under commerce stream.
- 2) To know the interest of students in commerce.
- 3) To develop the sufficient knowledge to make them employable.
- 4) To know the satisfaction level of their stream.

Methodology Applied

The research is developed through observation and collection of data through questionnaires. The sample size is determined as 50 students.

Statistical tool:

To analyze the data X^2 technique, correlation and bar chart is used and tried to bring conclusion from this analysis.

Performance indicator for the students

1) Knowledge

Through education we will come to know the various aspects of the different areas of the stream. That will helps to develop a new knowledge in the minds of the students and also helps to understand the basic.

2) Develop Professionalism

Higher education creates qualified professionals like CA, Managers, Industrialist and Academician etc. These are the courses that build professionalism in their career.

3) Identify career option.

The different sectors of the commerce and management can be identified easily if the person is educated. It makes easy to that person to select the particular job that he is interested most in that work.

4) Self employment

Under this discipline he has knowledge about each and every type of the industry and business. So there is a much scope for him to establish his own business or develop the small scale industry and create employment opportunity for the others.

5) Team work.

In each organization to perform better he has to work in a team. Industry recognises its efficiency through efficiency of their team. If you develop a good team work, that will prove your efficiency in your performance.

6) Strategy formulation.

To start any project, the basic requirement is they have to frame a strategy. According to the strategy they have to execute each and every aspect for implementing that plan. The role of a strategic planner will play major aspect in the industry.

7) Case Analysis

The present happening in the business world presented in the form of case. Students have to go through that live case and analyse it to bring solution to solve that case. Here students are come to know how to solve the problems that are daily issue in the industry.

8) Leadership

Inspiring the students by telling success stories of great leaders in the business field, will make the students to follow the footsteps of the leaders. This will encourage them to build leadership quality from the students day its self.

9) Risk analysis

Every business has to take risk to survive in the market. If the business man able to understand the risk that he has to take in the various segment of business then he will invest his capital through careful analysing various factors. This makes risk analysis will take crucial factor in the business.

10) Ethical Value

Each person has to develop ethical values in their trading or work. If you practice a good ethical practice in your business means, you will get a better return for your investment.

11) Communication :

To market your qualification and place in a good company communication will play major role. Commerce sector majorly depends on the public to understand the needs and convince of your client you require good communication.

12) Positive thinking

Commerce mainly depends on the market condition. If there is any fluctuation in the market will rectify in your work. There for students has to develop positive attitude in their work culture.

13) Technology Usage

Now in a modern world each work will depends on the technology. Up gradation of your skill to meet the requirement of sophisticated technology is must. To develop the career he must be very flexible to adopt the changing technology.

14) Presentation in Conference

Prepare the students to present the papers in the national and international seminar it will make the students to gain a new knowledge in different field and also helps to build confidence in the minds of the students.

15) Organize fest

Organizing a fest will guide the students in various aspects like train them as an organizer, handle responsibility, hospitality, time management etc.

16) Create interest on research

Students should be inspired by the faculty members to develop the research paper that will create value addition to themselves and the society.

17) Overview of Industry

Under this they will come to know the various levels of management. They have the opportunity to learn more on industry according to your preference, industrial knowledge makes the students easily place able in the market.

18) Work shop on aptitude skill:

At present in the job market we can see that for any type of the job aptitude exams are common. So to make our students strong in aptitude area we have to provide training to them to get success in the competitive exams.

Hypothesis: Conferences and seminars will encourage the students to gain more insight about subjects and generation of new knowledge to develop them self.

Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total
Male	12	8	5	0	0	25
Female	16	6	3	0	0	25
Total	28	14	8	0	0	50

f_0	f_e	$(f_0 - f_e)^2 / f_e$
12	14	.2857
13	11	.3636
16	14	.2857
9	11	.3636
Total		1.2986

Here the X^2 value 1.298 falls under acceptance region there for accept the null hypotheses from this we can conclude that students taking seriously seminars and conferences to develop their career.

Hypothesis: There is a Sufficient guidelines required to place them better position.

Gender	Group Discussion	Knowledge	Presentation skill	Aptitude skill	Total
Male	22	24	24	25	95
Female	23	24	23	25	95
Total	45	48	47	50	190

f_0	f_e	$(f_0 - f_e)^2 / f_e$
22	22.5	.0111
24	24	0
24	23.5	.0106
25	25	0
23	22.5	.0111
24	24	0
23	23.5	.0106

25	25	0
		.0434

Here the X^2 value .0434 falls under acceptance region so accept the null hypothesis from this we can conclude that students requires Sufficient guidelines required to place them better position.

Interest of the students in the different fields of the commerce and management

Particulars	No of Respondents	% of Respondents
Banking	32	64
Insurance	3	6
MNC	6	12
Self employment	3	6
Media	2	4
Others	4	8
Total	50	100

Inference

From this graph it's clear that majority of the students are interested to join banking sectors because there is a lot of openings we can find at present in the banking sector

Higher education has to be focused on the present needs of the industry to meet the requirement of the various companies.

Particulars	Male (X)	Female (Y)	X ²	Y ²	XY
Strongly Agree	18	19	324	361	342
Agree	6	6	36	36	36
Neutral	1	0	1	0	0
Disagree	0	0	0	0	0
Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	0
Total	25	25	361	397	378

$$\begin{aligned}
 r &= \frac{n \sum XY - \sum X \times \sum Y}{\sqrt{n \sum X^2 - \sum (X)^2} \times \sqrt{n \sum Y^2 - \sum (Y)^2}} \\
 &= \frac{5 \times 378 - (25 \times 25)}{\sqrt{(5 \times 361 - 25^2) \times (5 \times 397 - 25^2)}} \\
 &= \frac{1265}{\sqrt{1180 \times 1360}} \\
 &= \frac{1265}{1267} \\
 &= .9984
 \end{aligned}$$

From this analysis it's clear that there is a positive correlation between X and Y variable it shows that higher education has to design the curriculum as per the needs of the industry.

Findings:

1. Higher education should help the students to develop basic foundation regarding the industry.
2. Seminars and workshops will help the students to gain more knowledge about the advanced issues in their stream.
3. Higher education prepares the students by dating their skills according to the present requirement of the job market.
4. Higher education should teach the students to cultivate team spirit in every work.
5. Commerce education develops more entrepreneurs to solve the unemployment problem.
6. Majority of the students opt for banking sector under commerce education.

Suggestion:

1. Higher education has to give opportunity to students to do the work in innovative way.
2. Higher education has to develop skill based training programme to the students.
3. Commerce education should adopt flexibility in designing syllabus according to the changes takes place in the present scenario.
4. Industrial visit helps the students to understand the day today activities of the company.
5. Students has to use latest techniques like e journal, e book, commerce and management related web sites these helps the students to develop their knowledge.

Conclusion

Now a days there is a lot of demand for commerce and management education so each institution has to make a strategy that how they can improve the commerce and management education to place their students in better position. Every institution has to give importance to develop soft skills of the students. That will help them to develop their career.

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Paper 13

STUDENTS PERCEPTION AND SATISFACTION ON GOOGLE PAY APP WITH REFERENCE TO SELECTED COLLEGES IN MANGALORE

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Abstract:

Cashless transactions are on the verge of increase in the present days. Most of the people find it very convenient to carry out their transactions without any kind of risk. Digital payments are very fast & the amount will be credited to the receivers account instantly. Transaction can be done anytime, anywhere without any requirements of documents. In the present day economic state financial transactions are carried out in digital form without the presence of physical cash. Easiest mode to carry out digital payment transactions is by using payment apps. It has emerged as an important tool in advancing financial inclusion because of lower transaction costs & safety & convenience of making payments.

Keywords: Transactions, convenient, digital payments, financial transactions, physical cash & payment apps.

Introduction:

After looking into the developed economic set up & the advancements in technology, it was decided to put much initiatives on cashless payments. A new organization called National payments corporation of India (NPCI) was set up in the year 2008. NPCI started its operations with the guidance & support of RBI. It also functions as a hub for all electronic payments of the country. Due to increasing demand for electronic transactions, unified payments interface (UPI) had brought about the new mile stone with rapidly increasing number of transactions on day to day basis across the country. In this payments can be made without sharing bank details. Therefore, it is considered as faster, safer, quick & efficient transactions for any number of transactions.

Google pay is UPI based app to provide cashless and seamless payment experience. This app helps to make hassle free, secure payment directly from the bank account. This facility is available round the clock. Google pay app is also used for shopping at favorite destinations, refunds and cash back etc.

WORKING OF GOOGLE PAY APP

It is initially necessary to download this app on app store (Google pay payment service powered by yes bank). After downloading registering your bank account number becomes necessary. After registration app asks which bank user wants to link the same and you need to click on your banks logo and it automatically shows your account, number as your phone number is linked to bank account, it is detected by using UPI data base. It is safe to use Google pay or any other UPI app. But in case of entering layer amounts it may be bit difficult

due to security issues usually affect such wallet sites and app. User has to add only that amount of money which he wishes to spend and keep the wallet empty for most of the time.

UPI is initiated by National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) with the support of RBI and Indian Banks Association (IBA). It avoids traditional online transfers using account name, number, IFSC code etc. with UPI it is enough if recipients VPA (Virtual Payment Address) is known. UPI payment is advanced version of IMPS (Immediate Payment Service). Presently 29 banks have agreed to use this service.

In this payment method accounts from all the banks and mobile numbers are at one place. When SMS is sent from your mobile number for verification, it finds all details of associated bank accounts as well. Click on bank name, it will display your bank account number. MPIN generated is matched with your VPA only then the transfer happens.

ADVANTAGES OF GOOGLE PAY APP

The following advantages are seen in using this app

- 1) Seamless transaction
- 2) Proper record of repayments
- 3) Save time and resources
- 4) Less transaction costs
- 5) Transparency & security
- 6) Inclusive growth
- 7) Utility bill payments & insurance premium payments

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- 1) To study the mechanism of Google, pay app
- 2) To analyze the perception of students on Google pay app
- 3) To study the satisfaction level of students after using Google pay app
- 4) To understand the benefits of Google, pay app
- 5) To give necessary suggestions based on findings of study

METHODOLOGY USED

Type of sample used in the study is convenient sampling, area chosen for the study is Ujire town specially pertaining to S D M college campus limits only. Types of audience targeted are students who use Google pay app for making payments. Size of the sample is restricted to one hundred respondents taken out from degree, post-graduation and engineering colleges of S D M institutions.

Data for this study is collected from both primary and secondary source. Primary data is collected from questionnaires given to the respondents. Secondary data is collected from books, journals and related sites. The collected data is then tabulated and further analyzed.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Uses of apps for making payments is very new to developing economy like India and are used by few students today. What is required is spreading awareness and educating students and young people to use payment apps. This will lead to reduced risks of carrying and receiving cash, risks of fraud etc. It is also possible to maintain proper documents in case if concerned people claim or demand arrears of their payments. At present one is required to carry his smart phone downloaded with this app. If a payment is to be made or other transactions like payment of utility bills, DTH recharge, payment of insurance premium, & other payments to be made to the respective parties. in any kind of occasions. In the years to come number of people using the app will increase irrespective of gender, place (area) and

educational level. Common people will start using these apps like Google pay to make their payments and get acclimatized with the same.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- 1) Only student's community is taken for the study
- 2) Only selected colleges (leading institutions) is taken in this study. Specifically, students from degree, post-graduation and engineering are considered. Selected colleges are Canara group & Srinivas group of institutions only.
- 3) Size of the sample is restricted to one hundred respondents. 30 from degree, 20 from PG and the rest 50 from engineering college

DATA ANALYSIS

Data is analyzed using the responses taken from the respondents. Detailed analysis is as follows

Table 1: Age of the respondents

Age (in years)	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
18 – 20	36	36
21 -23	58	58
Above 23	06	06
Total	100	100

Table 2: Gender of the respondents

Gender	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Male	80	80
Female	20	20
Total	100	100

Table 3: Course of studying

Course	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Degree	30	30
PG	20	20
Engineering	50	50
Total	100	100

Table 4: Approximate pocket money received (per month)

Rupees (In 000's)	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Up to 5	30	30
6 – 10	46	46
Above 10	24	24
Total	100	100

Table 5: Source of recommendation to use Google pay wallet

Source	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Bank officials	48	48
Relatives & friends	22	22
Websites	30	30
Total	100	100

Table 6: Awareness level of respondents on Google pay wallet app

Awareness level	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly aware	21	21
Aware	53	53
Somewhat aware	26	26
Total	100	100

Table 7: Purpose of using Google pay app

Purpose	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Making payments	42	42
Transferring funds	36	36
Both	22	22
Total	100	100

Table 8: Perception rating of respondents for Google pay app

Perception rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	08	08
Good	36	36
Average	40	40
Satisfactory	16	16
Total	100	100

Table 9: Satisfaction level of respondents

Satisfaction level	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly satisfied	30	30
Satisfied	47	47
Not satisfied	23	23
Total	100	100

Table 10: Respondents rating of following parameters

a) Bill payments

Rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	10	10
Good	30	30
Average	26	26
Satisfactory	34	34
Total	100	100

b) Fund transfer

Rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	06	06
Good	18	18
Average	55	55
Satisfactory	21	21
Total	100	100

c) Efficiency of transactions

Rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	07	07
Good	19	19
Average	52	52
Satisfactory	22	22
Total	100	100

d) Time taken for completing transactions

Rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	04	04
Good	21	21
Average	50	50
Satisfactory	25	25
Total	100	100

e) Rectifying technical issues

Rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	06	06
Good	14	14
Average	48	48
Satisfactory	32	32
Total	100	100

f) Safety and security

Rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	10	10
Good	32	32
Average	41	41
Satisfactory	17	17
Total	100	100

g) Call center/ Toll free / Dedicated team

Rating	Number of respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	06	06
Good	13	13
Average	35	35
Satisfactory	46	46
Total	100	100

Findings of this study:

The following are the findings observed in this study, as far as this payment app is concerned.

- 1) Majority of the respondents are in the age group of 21-23 years.
- 2) 80% of the respondents taken in this study are males.
- 3) Majority of the respondents taken in this study are from engineering courses.
- 4) Majority of the respondents taken in this study receive their pocket money in the range of six to ten thousand rupees.

- 5) Respondents major source of recommendations for using google pay app is their bank officials themselves.
- 6) 53% of the respondents are aware about google pay app used for making payments.
- 7) 42% of the respondents use this app for making payments.
- 8) 40% of the respondents have their perception rating on this app as average.
- 9) 47% of the respondents are satisfied after using google pay app.

SUGGESTIONS

Following are the major suggestions taken out from the responses given by the respondents.

- 1) Cash back offers given for payment transfers must be realistic in nature.
- 2) Server problems are more detected from the banks side due to which transfer may not happen or may get delayed, but on the other hand it causes inconvenience to the users. This has to be avoided.
- 3) Options given under google pay app can also be included in this app too. This may require updating; the sooner it is done more will be the convenience & more are the chances of increasing the number of users.

CONCLUSION

Banking system has undergone a major change in the very recent years. Within a couple of years, we expect more & more changes in the way in which the transaction will be carried out by the customers. Everything depends on the quality of services rendered & the relationship maintained with the clients. Clients want on time service, if the same is provided on time they remain happy. At present most of the customers use digital payment apps for making payments, best out of best banking customers. Despite looking at the present trend demand for cashless transactions are increased compared with the previous years. Youngsters prefer more payments to be made cashless by using payment apps. These apps are safe, convenient & has higher relevance because it carries valid documentary evidence.

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Paper 14

**AN ANALYSIS ON TRAINING THE INNOVATIVE
MINDS TOWARDS SUCCESSIVE STEP IN BUSINESS
WORLD. “BADA BUSINESS PVT. LTD.”- A CASE
STUDY.**

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Abstract:

India is known for its youth power. As half of the Indian population is young minds that is 600 millions who are under 25 years old . So youth is the power of India. Where as dynamically, innovative and creative minds are working towards the growth of India in all directions and even in “Business”. When it comes to Business, we can find many innovative entrepreneurs (A person who makes money by starting or running business , especially when this involves taking financial risk.) Profit or Loss , Growth or Fall is the part and parcel of any business firm its a Universal protocol. In this paper we discuss about the company Bada Business pvt. Ltd. Whose main motive is to train the rising entrepreneur, train the proprietor’s of small business and help them to expand there business magnificiantly . This is a company with a innovative idea of Motivation and training the entrepreneur by advicing, clearing there thoughts , providing different modes and sources of knowledge and sharing experience so that they will not hesitate in stepping up to a new phase in there Business . Even sharpen there skill towards their betterment. We analyse about the working and benefits of this company to us.

Keywords: Entrepreneur training , Young minds, Motivation, Growth, Knowledge, Experience.

Introduction:

Bada Business pvt ltd. Is the Educational training platform focuses on burning problem of Entrepreneurs and aspiring entrepreneur's. Bada business aims to empower every Indian businessmen to convert their small business into big business . This platform is bridging the Educational infrastructure gap by providing readymade video solutions ,engaging forums that also acts as a customised solutions from uber of consultants and continues business learnings. This company enables instant hand holding solutions from one another and also by consultants. Has at present we can find many training institutions for management and business, but this company “A Training platform “ even trains the needy. That means in todays competitive world all are running behind money making but this company provides a pocket friendly training service to all. Which is more profitable for people with aspiration of learning but who cant afford high fees structure. Here they can get best education by experienced and even in there budget. Bada Business pvt. Ltd. is a private company incorporated on 24th January 2019. And it is registered at registrar of companies Delhi. It is a service oriented company. Which has only one

motive, is to educate all, seeking help and need of knowledge related to business. This Service is also available in various languages. This company trains people who have joined it , in all directions of business subjects and areas. From How to start , to developing a business, sales , Marketing, Human Resource management, legal ,Information Technology, Digital Marketing, Leadership, Product & Services, Retail, Executions and Strategies. Dr. Vivek Bindra is the founder and CEO of Bada Business pvt. ltd. He is a Revolutionary Entrepreneur, an Internationally acclaimed Motivational Speaker and a Business coach . He is a trusted Advicer for more than 1500+ corporate houses and Entrepreneurs. And he is also a recipient of more than 100 Globally Admired Awards .

- Even he has a YouTube channel named Dr. Vivek Bindra , he has more than 10 million subscribers . It is Worlds most subscribed , Entrepreneur YouTube channel. And upward of 50 crore viewership.

- There is even a application, named Badabusiness app- Where including Vivek Bindra 50+ National and Internationally well-known company CEO's , MD's , Board of Directors, Vice-president, Board Members etc. , share there experiences. And a bundle of knowledge is shared which motivates and educates all the users about business and its related factors. Dr. Vivek Bindra's Vision is to empower Indian entrepreneur's and to convert small business into big business. And his mission is to bridge the Educational infrastructure gap and to make the management and Entrepreneurship education affordable. Which is one of highlighting point which gains high attention and support from all. As the education has become one of the need of the people which all have the motivation of learning but no one can afford it because of financial instability and also the hight fees structure.

Pranauned personalities who are connected with this firm-

- We can listen the words and experiences of people-
 - Mr. Mahesh Gupta , Chairman Kent Health care products.
 - Mr. Ashish Chauhan , CEO & MD of Bombay Stock Exchange.
 - Mr. Ramesh Agarwal , Chairman Agarwal Movers & Packers Ltd.
 - Mr. Keki Mistery , Vice Chairman & CEO of HDFC.
 - Mr. Hari Om Rai , Chairman of LAVA.
 - Mr. Manu Jain , India Head & Global Vice president of Xiaomi.
 - Mr. Lalit Agarwal , MD & Chairman of V-Mart .
 - Balakrishna Gurug , Patanjali
 - Mr. Sanjiv Bajaj , Vice Chairman & MD of Bajaj Capital.
 - Mr. Alfred Ford , Board Member of Ford Motors Company.

And many more.....

We can listen maximum, sharing there experiences and saying Bada Business pvt. Ltd. has also helped them in there growth , Thanking Dr. Vivek Bindra .

Highlighting points of the business-

It is Indias only entrepreneurship training program available in Hindi and other regional languages.

Worlds most affordable Entrepreneurship training program.

Gets an opportunity to learn from the leaders who have built billion dollar business.

Learn from the experts of worlds finest and big universities.

Objectives & Benefits :

- Learn from the experienced and Industry leaders who have built billion dollar business.
- Business Strategy framework from Leadership Funnel program
- Subject matter experts from Worlds best Universities.
- It generates business leads from yourself .
- Generates innovation and Self thinking.
- Known for creating Free Learning University in YouTube.

Research Methodology :

Based on the Primary and Secondary data this case study has been developed, both sources are taken into consideration for data collection. As per the students and people who have personally attended the seminars of Vivek Bindra and even people using Badabusiness app , there personal views and experiences are taken into consideration. And even business journals , and newspapers articles following the headlined articles are read clearly for transparent view about the company Bada Business pvt ltd.

Marketing Strategies :

Reaching people by there own source “Social Media “

[0% investment in marketing]

Advertising through Social Media [Instagram , YouTube , Facebook, Snapchat.]

Free learning University in YouTube and in there application.

- They are providing a very affordable course for 2 years :

For Professionals	36000/-
For Women	24000/-
For Students	18000/-

Competitors Analysis :

There are many competitors-

- 1) edx
- 2) Coursera
- 3) MIT open courses
- 4) Mr. Ujjwal Pathani (Motivational speaker)

There are many top Management Universities, many Online courses and even many other Motivational speakers who train and motivate people about business and Entrepreneurship. But Bada Business Pvt. Ltd. Stand different by its very affordable fees structure

that even a middleclass family member interested can afford it and get the total benefit through it. This is the starting point which attracts millions.

- And learning from others experiences is the best book of knowledge.

SWOT Analysis :

Strength :

- Most affordable price structure which attracts most people.
 - Helps in Indian Economy Development.
 - Large and growing network of people seeking management skills.

Weakness :

- Weak Marketing Strategies.
 - Not easily approachable by people.

Opportunities :

- Great opportunities to people to expand their existing business and to gain Management Skills.
- It can grow Globally (There is a lot more need of fine skills of Management and Business.)

Threats :

- Duplication of Idea.
- Increasing Competitors

Conclusion:

In today's competitive world all are educated, but we can find companies complaining that there are many educated available but lack of skill. India is a country with huge youth crowd and all have that fire in them to do something in their life but somewhere because of financial issues they drawback their education and won't complete their dream because they can't afford management or business courses. Bada Business pvt ltd is a best platform to them, as they provide the finest and best training in very reasonable fees structure. This training has changed many people's life, and also skilled and sharpened their potential to the best. This is one of the emerging and most demanded management business training programs among youth and others at present time.

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Paper 15

IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EXISTENCE EACH DAY

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Abstract

In the modern world, artificial intelligence continues to evolve dramatically with day by day new and improved innovations. The computers have now been designed to perform simple tasks such as vehicle identification, facial recognition and many more. The major goal of AI is the development of sophisticated and dramatically more complicated systems to outperform individuals in any way. This involves performing more difficult tasks such as chess-playing and finding solutions for equations. The major goal of AI is to improve all human activities as well as to provide better alternatives than human being solves an issue. The automated system, which carries out all human activities, from vehicle control to computerized commercial applications, will face a number of challenges in the future. However, it prevents the production of lethal weapons that once used to strike, harm people noticeably. The development of super Artificial intelligence, which improves self, triggers an intelligence explosion, however would greatly discontinue human intellectual ability. The development of super AI is the largest breakthrough in human existence history. The development of advanced technology thus contributed significantly to the removal of conflicts, effective means of disease prevention and application development. In this paper, we analyze the influence of AI on our daily lives, as well as various things such as AI's growth, AI's challenges, applications of AI in various aspects of life and Artificial Intelligence ethics.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Technology, Performance, Automated System.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the modern and industrial world, artificial intelligence (AI) becomes an important aspect of our day to day existence. Such a technique is applied in all industries, from the healthcare sector to the military to reduce human intervention and to achieve better and quicker outcomes. We are lucky to live in the scientific innovation age. Today we live in a world in which computers & algorithms carry on a great deal of work. Within today's growth, AI has a unique position[1]. While we learn AI is the study of the development of human knowledge in machines and computers. The robots can do some easy to complicated tasks in this system, as we humans have routinely to do. In many ways, the AI systems can reduce human activity. Many of them use artificial intelligence to implement different operations throughout the field and generate computers with various activities on a regular basis. The use of artificial intelligence helps make the work fast and more efficient.

2. AI'S GROWTH[2]

- 1950: Software expert John McCarthy discovers "artificial intelligence."

- 1998: Furby, an interactive doll manufactured by Tiger Electronics, and later Hasbro, which imitates learning languages and personality development, brings AI to the public. The more you practice and the way you perform, the more your temperament will be affected.
- 2000: The Massachusetts Institute of Technology's associate Professor Cynthia Breazeal creates Kismet, a robot head which can express human facial movements in response to interactions.
- 2009: The self-driving Google car project has been created.
- 2015-2017: Google AlphaGo DeepMind defeats Go winners respectively Fan Hui, Lee Sedo and Ke Jie.
- 2016: Google's auto-driving car initiative will turn into Waymo, a hardware self-driving service.
- 2017: Stephen Hawking reports of the "worst in civilizing history" creation of artificial intelligence.
- 2018: Elon Musk, CEO of Tesla and SpaceX, said artificial intelligence could build an 'immortal tyrant' while CEO of Google, Sundar Pichai, said it's "among the most valuable things in which society is operating."

3. REASONS FOR WHY ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IS CURRENTLY POPULAR.

- **All are connected[3]:** All are related now in the environment and the artificial intelligence sector is that to an unprecedented degree, as a consequence of this accelerated digitalization. The Web links most of the artifacts in our universe. This is all the more important for artificial intelligence.
- **Cheaper computing[3]:** The amount required for AI is immense. Therefore, it was difficult to even a decade earlier to conceive for an AI-driven future because there was no computational spare capacity at an economical cost. The AWS platform has cut prices more than fifty times, making operating a computer network at the high degree very affordable.
- **Information is the new oil[3]:** Machine learning and, in particular, deep learning, relies explicitly on the volume of data we provide. The better it gets the more intelligent the data the machine provides.
- **Machine learning is really the new normal[3]:** Machine learning is transformative, industry by industry, and it is very important to apply technologies to exploit the domain. Today we can see artificial intelligence and machine learning are the new normal, irrespective of the industry or domain.
- **The ability to conquer all industries[3]:** Artificial intelligence strength are such that due to all the omnipresence of the market, it is able to disrupt any other industry vertically. During the next five years growing business field is inevitably interrupted, without exception, because of the vast complexity of the AI market and the sub-domains of deep learning.
- **Infinite benefits and we just scratch the surface[3]:** There are endless possibilities to any use of artificial intelligence. During the process of a quick upward rise, we can also see that we're at the beginning of unlimited potential of an AI sector.

4. AI'S CHALLENGES

- **Building trust[4]:** AI works on the technical side, many of which are unfruitful and understandable.

- **AI Human Interface[4]:** Enterprise without qualified professionals employed with this technology has been rising with the advent of AI.
- **Investment[4]:** AI is an expensive development in which not every owner of the business company is able to invest capital.
- **Computer malfunction[4]:** It is difficult to recognize the source of failures and malfunctions of computers and algorithms running AI.
- **Many functions only may be replaced[4]:** AI has its own limits like any other technology; it certainly cannot substitute all activities.
- **Strong aspirations[4]:** Not everyone realizes how AI operates and may have quite high functioning standards as well.

5. IN VARIOUS ASPECTS OF LIFE AI APPLICATIONS

The technology of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning are being extremely used to examine human comportment in order to enable apps to determine what and when consumers want it. Such applications make it much easier to order food, watch movies & listen to music[5]. Here are some instances of AI's daily life improvement:

- **Home security[5]:** Try AI optimized alarm and camera systems if you would like cutting-edge home protection. Such applications are used to create a list of tourists in your home through computer learn and face recognition tools. It encourages the machine to immediately identify visitors. AI-powered surveillance is an early step towards homemaker automation, providing many other functions, including the warning of children's arrival from school as well as the control of animals' movements. Such devices can even independently alert emergency services, making them a better substitute to other service based on subscription.
- **Digital media[5]:** For entertainment, machine learning has enormous potential and has already been used for streaming services such as Google Play, Netflix and Amazon Prime. Such services leverage algorithms that function as neural networks to remove low-quality retrieval and buffering, which provides high-quality information in your Internet provider. Medium production also supports algorithms powered by AI. AI algorithms have already been developed to increase efficiency of news stories.
- **Self-driving cars[5]:** The production of auto-driving cars is driven by AI systems. According to Online research, AI-powered vehicles already exceed human drivers in security, since AI enables self-conductive vehicles to adjust instantly and learn from different situations. Many car manufacturers already want to introduce AI technologies into future products.
- **Ride-sharing apps[5]:** Ride sharing apps like Uber use AI to change the time required to carry passengers to the target destination. The technology allows consumers to know how much longer they will travel when their driver will get there and also how long it will need to be shipped.
- **Fraud prevention[5]:** Banks use AI to submit Smartphone alerts to assist in fraud detection. If you have an exceptionally large transaction on your record, your account may be noted and you might be questioned to validate buying if you have issued alerts on your mobile or if shopping takes place in a city far away from home. AI helps these advisories to recognize suspicious trends in your buying activity by examining your typical daily purchases.
- **Music recommendations[5]:** Streaming music apps use AI to test your auditory patterns. The app uses data to suggest more compositions. Spotify delivers tips for recent releases, old favorites, and new findings based on your listening habits. Google Play also provides

smart playlists recommendations, using the strength of AI to take into account factors like current weather that give music the right mood.

6. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ETHICS.

Optimization of transportation, fraud detection, design, analysis, and translation: smart computer systems make our lives better. The planet becomes more effective, and therefore better, as these devices become more competent. Technology giants like Amazon, Facebook, IBM, Alphabet and Microsoft—and others like Stephen Hawking or Elon Musk—believe it's time to speak about the almost limitless artificial intelligence environment[6]. In many cases, it's just as critical as it's in emerging technologies for ethics & risk evaluations.

1. **Unemployment[6]:** The job system mostly involves technology. We also built methods of automating labor, and we are now making room to take on more nuanced tasks, transitioning from pre-industrial physical labor to conceptual work in our globalised world, which characterizes strategic and managerial function.
2. **Inequality[6]:** The reward of participation towards the market is our economy, mostly measured on the basis of a salary. In products and services, the majority of enterprises even now depend on daily work. But a corporation will dramatically reduce its reliance on human labour by using artificial intelligence, and this ensures the profits will go downward with less workers. As a consequence, citizens who are owned by AI-driven companies would make any income.
3. **Artificial stupidity[6]:** Whether you are person or machine, knowledge comes from understanding. Systems generally have a testing period in which the best architectures are "learned" to identify and react accordingly. After a system is completely developed, it can be checked and we will see how it does with more scenarios.
4. **Racist robots[6]:** Although artificial intelligence is ability for pace and computation far beyond the capability of humanity, justice and neutrality are not always trustworthy. In Google's Photos Platform, AI will be used to identify a person, artefacts or images, with Google as well as its parent company, Alphabet, among the pioneers in artificial intelligence. But it could go bad if a camera fails to recognize racial sensitivity, or if a program used to predict the future offenders is unfair to Black people.
5. **Security[6]:** The better a device, the more it could be used for bad and good purposes. It refers to AI systems which may cause damage if they are deceptive and are not only created to substitute man-made soldiers or automated weapons. Because the fight is not just going to be defeated on the battlefield, cyber security is gaining in importance. After all, we have to deal with either a system which is faster and larger than us.
6. **Evil genies[6]:** We need to think about it not only adversaries. What about artificial intelligence itself? It does not mean bringing "evil" throughout the way human force or in the manner that Hollywood cinemas show IA disasters. We can instead see a state-of-the-art AI program as "a bottle of genius" which can meet expectations but which has horrible unanticipated implications.
7. **Singularity[6]:** The reason that people are at the food chain is not that they have muscles or sharp teeth. Human ingenuity and intellect are almost entirely the explanation for human conquest. They may enhance livestock by designing and using the equipment to handle them, including functional devices such as containers and arms and cognitive resources such as training and preparation.
8. **Robot rights[6]:** Although neuroscientists often seek to unlock the secrets of experienced memory, we grasp more of the underlying processes of incentive and hate. This function is associated with even simple animals. In some respects, in artificial intelligence applications we are developing specific incentive and avoidance processes.

Enhanced learning, for the instance, is analogous to dog training: increased success of simulated recompense is boosted.

7. CONCLUSION

To sum up, by artificial intelligence & data analysis, the planet is on the brink of revolutionizing multiple businesses. Significant implementations also improved decision-making, risk mitigation, business models and efficiency of banking, national security, criminal justice, health care, infrastructure and cities. Strong economic and social gains arise from these changes. Nevertheless, the way AI systems are designed has significant implications for the entire society. It is important to find ways to address policy issues, to overcome ethical disputes, to settle legal challenges and to achieve consistency in AIs & data analytics solutions. The manner decisions were made and how they are implemented into corporate processes impacts individual preferences in technological technologies. It is precisely how these processes are performed that needs to be better grasped because they will have a significant impact on the public in the near future. AI can be a technology-related breakthrough and the only human innovation of its kind in history.

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